

**University of
Zurich** ^{UZH}

**Master of Advanced Studies
European and Chinese Business
Management**

MAS thesis
presented to the Faculty of Business, Economics and Informatics
of the University of Zurich
for the degree of

**Master of Advanced Studies UZH
in European and Chinese Business Management**

*Energy Policies within Two Systems:
A Comparative Analysis of Germany and China through Porter's Competitiveness Model*

Authors:

Regina Fernández

Kaixin He

Xiyang Li

Thesis Supervisor:

Olga E. Annushkina, PhD, MBA

SDA Bocconi School of Management

Strategy and Entrepreneurial Department

Submission date: 15.06.2020

Declaration Form

The work we have submitted is our own effort. We certify that:

- All the material in this thesis which is not our own work has been identified and acknowledged. No materials are included for which a degree has been previously conferred upon us.
- The authors have equally contributed to the present thesis work

Student name: Regina Fernandez Hernandez

Signed Date: ~~Regina Fernandez~~ 15.06.20

Student name: Kaixin He

Signed Date: 15.06.20

Student name: Xiyang Li

Signed Date: 15.06.20

Abstract

According to civil societies and international organizations, mitigating climate change needs urgent global action now. In this master thesis we present a policy evaluation of climate-related policies in Germany and China, with a close-up view at their adaptation in two chosen cities, Freiburg and Suining. We test whether both regions are using the best of their resources to promote and to gain international competitive advantage in the green energy industry. By reviewing relevant theories and quantitative data analysis of the two particular countries, the research is conducted through a qualitative comparative analysis of green energy policies. To meet economic and sustainable growth goals, countries need to compare and evaluate what economic approaches must be taken in the short term for a long-term perspective. By adapting Porter's theory of competitiveness of nations we ask: How are the international and national institutional frameworks designed to help cities adapt to climate change transition? And what can we learn from Porter's competitiveness model in reference to cities and nations to become global leaders in the green energy industry?

To find answers, we research whether nations could bring to cities the necessary capacity of effective and resilient energy policies to fight the global climate crisis through innovation. We analyze what are the states' energy policies for climate change at the national level and how these are applied on the city level. The findings of the discussions presented in our thesis confirm the initial hypothesis that nations can become more competitive through new ways of innovation in the green energy industry. As the analysis through the prism of Porter's Model also makes visible, cities can acquire a more inclusive green model thanks to national competitiveness and innovation-driven techniques. We also observe that although both cities follow different political strategies on green energies, both have also created local demand and sufficient resources and factor conditions to develop a green energy ecosystem. As a possible recommendation, we encourage that cities—and nations—create synergies and partnerships between each other, where they can prioritize challenges and learn from each other's experiences for a common green future.

Table of Contents

<i>Declaration Form</i>	<i>ii</i>
<i>Abstract</i>	<i>iii</i>
<i>List of Figures and Tables</i>	<i>v</i>
1. Introduction	1
2. Literature Review	5
3. Research Methodology	10
4. Energy Policies within Two Systems: Germany and China in Comparison	13
4.1. National-level Energy Policies in Germany	13
4.1.1. Germany’s Green Energy Overview	17
4.1.2. Energy Mix 2019.....	18
4.1.3. GHG Emissions.....	20
4.1.4. Share of solar and wind renewable energy sources.....	21
4.1.5. Local Energy Policies in Freiburg.....	22
4.2. National-level Energy Policies in China	24
4.2.1. China’s Green Energy Overview	29
4.2.2. China’s energy consumption structure 2017, 2018	31
4.2.3. GHG emissions	31
4.2.4. Share of nuclear and hydropower energy sources.....	32
4.2.5. Local Energy Policies in Suining	33
5. Discussion: Differences and Similarities in Green Energy Policies	35
5.1. Case Study of Freiburg	35
5.2. Case Study of Suining	39
5.3. Main Differences	43
5.4. Main Similarities	45
6. Conclusion	47
7. References	49

List of Figures and Tables

<i>Figure 1: Triple Sustainability Model</i>	7
<i>Figure 2: Theoretical framework at the core of the thesis</i>	9
<i>Figure 3: Germany’s greenhouse gas emissions 1850 – 2018 and reduction targets</i>	16
<i>Figure 4: Renewables’ share in gross power consumption 2019</i>	19
<i>Figure 5: Renewables’ share in gross power consumption 2019</i>	20
<i>Figure 6: Solar and wind energy in Germany – Installed capacity by postal code area megawatts per square mile, 2014 – 2050</i>	22
<i>Figure 7: Chinese CO₂ emissions by source, 1960-2018</i>	32
<i>Figure 8: Freiburg Green City Cluster</i>	36
<i>Figure 9: Suining City</i>	40
<i>Table 1: Germany’s Green Energy Overview</i>	18
<i>Table 2: China’s Green Energy Overview</i>	30

1. Introduction

Globally, one in ten people live in a community that has made statements for a Climate Emergency Declaration (hereafter CED). The first country to declare climate emergency was Australia in 2016, and small localities to entire countries, such as Ireland, Austria, Malta, Canada, Spain, and Argentina announced similar plans by 2019 too. Oxford dictionary defines climate emergency as ‘a situation in which urgent action is required to reduce or halt climate change and avoid potentially irreversible environmental damage resulting from it’ (Oxford Dictionary n.d.) On November 28, 2019, the European Parliament (hereafter EP) declared a climate and environmental emergency crisis (EP 2019). The EP urged all EU countries to commit to cut emissions by 55% by 2030 and become climate neutral by 2050 (Duch Guillot 2019). Also, China, one of the World’s largest CO₂ emitters, treats climate change more and more seriously. Although Chinese investment in renewable energy fell during the first quarter of 2019, it nonetheless ranks at the top of the list among countries’ investment in renewable energy (REN21 2019). Moreover, despite the fact that China is currently the global leader in renewable investment, is also the largest polluter. China is the world's largest CO₂ emitter, accounting for more than one-quarter of the total global emissions in 2017. After China, the list continues with the USA (15%), EU-28 (10%); India (7%); and Russia (5%) (Ritchie & Roser 2020). However, historically the United States has contributed most to global CO₂ emissions to date, accounting 25% of cumulative emissions. This is followed by the EU-28 (22%); China (13%); Russia (6%) and Japan (4%) (Ritchie & Roser). UN researchers understand that the rise of global temperatures is linked with the increase of CO₂ emissions (Ritchie & Roser).

Although Beijing had pledged that it would draw 20 % of its primary energy from non-fossil sources by 2030, it has also continued to fund investment through the Belt and Road Initiative (hereafter BRI), where state banks provide funds of USD 30 billion to build coal-based power plants in other countries. Because of this, global diplomatic pressure has been steadily growing on China to change course (Hook 2019). Even though in 2018, there is a decrease from the previous year, in overall there was a stable growth in renewable power capacity and China hold the leading position (32 %) of global total renewable investment, followed by Europe including Russia (21 %), the United States (17%) and Asia-Oceania (excluding China and India; 15%). Smaller shares were seen in India (5%), the Middle East and Africa (5%), the Americas

(excluding Brazil and the United States (3%); and Brazil (1%) (REN21 2019). Yet, experts alarm that the world is not on track to meet international and sustainable development goals:

‘Global trends continue to indicate that investing in renewable energy is investing in a profitable future. Investments in renewable energy in 2018 were three times higher than the amount invested in new coal and gas-fired generators,’ said Inger Andersen, Executive Director of the UN Environment Program. “While this is encouraging, we need to significantly step up the pace if we are to meet international climate & development goals’ (UN 2019).

Climate change or climate emergency needs now urgent action, according to civil societies and international organizations. During the first Conference of the Parties (hereafter COP) in 1992, a new framework was signed by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (hereafter UNFCCC). Following the announcement in December 2015, members of the UNFCCC at the COP 21 in Paris, confirmed—most recently—that the main goal is to keep global temperature well below 2 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels and to pursue efforts to limit the rise of temperature by 1.5 degrees Celsius (UNFCCC 2018). The agreement entered into force in November 2016. Since then, involved parties continue to work together to commit to fighting the climate change; they also recognized the need to strengthen knowledge, technologies, practices, and efforts of local communities and indigenous people, as well as the important role of providing incentives through tools such as domestic policies and carbon pricing (UNFCCC 2018). António Guterres, the current Secretary-General of the UN, spoke of four priorities that will be addressed in the next UN Climate Change Conference (COP 26 in Glasgow, initially planned for November 2020 but postponed to 2021 due to the Covid-19 pandemic): first, more ambitious national climate plans that will keep global warming temperatures well below pre-industrial levels; second, strategies to reach net-zero emissions by 2050; third, a comprehensive program of support for climate adaptation and resilience; and lastly, greater financing for sustainable green economy (UN 2020).

Economic growth is also linked historically to growing CO₂ emissions (Ritchie & Roser 2020). The carbon intensity of nearly all national economies has fallen in those economies that have shifted from coal dominated energy systems towards transforming economies. Such a shift is also likely to improve energy and technology efficiency as well as boost the overall capacity of renewable energy sources in use (Du, Lin & Xie 2017). To meet economic and sustainable growth goals, countries need to compare and evaluate what economic approaches must be taken in the short term for a long-term perspective. For green development investment activities there

are infrastructure projects which help to develop the economy, e.g., by fostering local renewable sources management and by covering solar energy supply internationally. However, it is not clear how countries will continue with their established policy frameworks to make the transition towards climate neutrality and economy as resilient as possible. The cases analyzed below offer a clear outlook of what challenges cities and countries currently face and how they seek attractive opportunities for reinvention, e.g., through new market strategies and feasible city policies to keep positive growth. Therefore, nations recently have driven their national competitiveness towards technological innovation in specific sectors to attract demand and supply. By doing so, they hope to become leaders in international competitiveness.

According to the Global Innovation Index (hereafter GII), Switzerland was and is the world's most innovative country, followed by Sweden, the USA, the Netherlands, and the UK (GII 2019). A recent report by the GII also underlines that the innovation gap between high-income economies and the rest of the world remains wide. Therefore, there are still imbalances in some countries such as China. The GII 2018 also confirms that wealthier countries have more diversified and export-oriented economies, and that, for the same reasons, there is a higher concentration of science and technology clusters in the USA (26 clusters), China (16 groups) and Germany (8) (GII 2018). The GII also highlighted the need to create advanced innovations in the energy sector, especially in aspects related to climate change targets and the growth of renewable energy demand. According to the International Energy Agency (hereafter IEA), by 2040 the world's energy requirements will increase by 30%; therefore, traditional fossil fuel methods are no longer sustainable. Only by developing new types of clean energy systems the demand and supply of sustainable capacity will be balanced and durable (IEA 2017).

In this thesis, we explore the main institutional framework and goals that are defined by relevant organizations on climate change in two chosen countries, China and Germany. We chose these two countries because both are global leaders in green energy while having very different approaches to it. We analyze what has been the impact of climate change on each of the two regions when it comes to economic, social and environmental outcomes. In more detail, our research focuses on green energies and sustainable development in two urban case studies of Freiburg and Suining. We chose these two cities primarily because both have been recognized as models of green cities for their respective regions. In the analysis, we make use of the Porter's Model to refer to the capacity of nations to gain competitive advantage in the energy industry and become global leaders in the renewable energy industry. We are inspired by the approach presented in Porter that encourages nations to use new ways of innovation through communities or clusters to gain in international competitiveness. Defining green cities or sustainable

development as an example of such ways allows for an understanding what are the tools that nations are missing in order to adapt to new green energy city models. By adapting Porter's theory of competitiveness of nations to the context of climate change policies in Germany and China, we ask: How are the international and national institutional frameworks designed to help cities adapt to climate change transition? And what can we learn from Porter's competitiveness model in reference to cities and nations to become global leaders in the green energy industry?

The analysis is precluded with a review of the relevant literature in the following section. It describes what has been already explored on how cities can address the challenges of climate change. It also mentions different attitudes towards the reasons why nations promote renewable investment. A discussion of the theoretical framework of the thesis is then also presented. In the subsequent methodology part, we analyze green energy policies from the point of view of institutional frameworks on climate change. We also evaluate the policies and directives of the two subject countries by using qualitative methods. We then proceed to developing a hypothesis of how nations can become more competitive through new ways of innovation in the energy industry. In this particular case, we test whether Germany or China could become more competitive internationally through adopting innovative techniques in their respective green energy ecosystems.

Points 4. and 5. make up the core analytical parts of this thesis. First, in the main findings and data analysis section, we focus in detail on the German and Chinese institutional regulations for climate change. We overview the national green energy policies adopted and consequently assess how both countries are adapting those policies to combat climate change. In the related discussion part, we present a closer look at two cities that have been named model examples of green cities in each country. We try to understand how the two cities have created their models of green energies by adapting to the national green energy policies or institutional frameworks. We engage with what has been described in Porter as a model of competitiveness in a specific industry to further explore how it is reflected on the city level. Thus, we test our hypothesis through a qualitative method. Finally, we compare both cities' policies on renewables sources, energy efficiency, and climate action plans for 2020, 2030 and 2050. All this allows us to understand for what reasons related to national competitiveness are Germany and China adopting international framework regulations on climate change.

2. Literature Review

A set of keywords (marked in italics in the following two paragraphs) needs to be defined before we engage in a deeper theoretical analysis.

Environmental stewardship has been defined as ‘an emphasis of sustainability, particularly ensuring that emissions from energy production do not exceed relevant absorptive capacities of relevant ecosystems’ (Gippen & Torney (2017:650). Already in the mid-twentieth century scholars called for environmental stewardship based on a land ethic ‘dealing with man’s relation to land and to the animals and plants which grow upon it’ (Leopold 1949:173). Related is a form of minimizing the consumption of energy in the cities for both people and the environment; thus, the concept of a *sustainable city* was created (Basiago 1996). The notion of a sustainable city has its roots also in the even earlier Garden City movement of the 1900s and the *ecological cities* of the 1970s. All these ideas were proposed as a new way of economic and human growth. Roseland (1997) defined the *eco-city* or the *sustainable communities* as a representation of a direction for community development. Since the 2000s, the political and economic elites have used the name green city interchangeably with that of a *smart city* to achieve broader economic growth and economic expansion as a way of eco-modernization while keeping energy and resources efficient and sustainable. Isenhour, McDonogh, and Checker (2015) showed how the well-being of the society is justified by maintaining economic and sustainable growth. They also provided arguments to claim that there is a way to have greater use of green technologies and sustainable designs for green cities, which will eventually reduce environmental harm.

We understand the green city as a concept that includes both international environmental values as well as concerns of social and economic development. This branding is well established as *going green* became synonymous with a strong focus on renewable energy policies. Moreover, it also refers to the opportunity of the communities and citizens to engage and benefit from the energy transition; it is to attract interested companies and skilled job seekers who are looking for new opportunities, and tourists who care about the environment and want to learn about green policies and technologies (REN21-REC 2019). The term *green* in itself is also full of (at times even contradictory) meanings but, in general, it refers to ‘investing in activities that, in an accessible context, can be considered suitable for the environment directly or indirectly’ (Chen 2019). *Green investment* is thus such a sustainable investment through which ‘companies seek to combat climate change and environmental destruction while promoting corporate responsibility’ (Investopedia n.d.). *Sustainable investments* have a broader meaning here too, as the term can also apply to an investment in

renewable energy and clean infrastructure projects as well as investing in key technologies such as district heating networks, electric vehicles (hereafter EV), storage technologies, and sector coupling (REN21-REC 2019). Finally, *green tech energy projects* relate to creating clean energy sources that are environmentally friendly with the usage of the newest technologies (Kenton 2019).

Cities and regional sustainable groups are creating models of synergies based on triple sustainability: economic, social and environmental (see figure 1, ECG n.d.). Nations have the know-how to create opportunities for investment in technology to develop better sources of clean, affordable, efficient, and accessible energy as a global economy. Most of the existing agendas on climate change are also based at the global level. Nations are defining their targets and goals on climate strategies based on international frameworks, e.g. such as the aforementioned UNFCCC. Climate change plays a vital role as the world is anticipating to prevent its impact on the global economy, our shared environment as well as on countless social and political issues. Fighting climate change and boosting economic resilience could provoke an increase in the competitive advantage of renewable energies industry and environmentalism values. In this way, national R&D, innovative techniques and technological development could be sufficient to fight climate change. Some authors thus argue that innovation is not the only driver of renewable investment, but climate change, energy security and economic growth are also key drivers (Ydersbond & Korsnes 2016:50). Other authors showed that the EU and Chinese authorities are adapting their energy policies based on frames of availability, efficiency, affordability and environmental stewardship (Gippner & Torney 2017). They also argued that environmental stewardship and climate change are political drivers important for developing more renewable and clean energy. In the case of China, the Medium- and Long-Term Renewable Energy Development Plan, published in September 2007, aimed to boost the country's self-sufficiency in terms of innovation by bringing in foreign technology in the short term and building up domestic innovation capacity in the longer term (NDRC 2007). At the same time, with the EU facing new changes in energy policies in the new millennium, the European Commission also proposed ideas of boosting innovation in the energy market (European Commission 2007).

(Source: Green Impact).

Figure 1: Triple Sustainability Model

There are various institutional frameworks based on international governance such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) and the UNFCCC. Yet, as Huang-Lachmann and Lovett (2016) explained, there are often many other local factors that shape decision making: conservative local governments, lack of an internal market, or high standards of technology that could lead governments to make different decisions. The theoretical core of the discussion presented in this thesis arises from a recognition of the duality of the issue. We follow the national competitiveness model as proposed by Porter (1990) to assess the picture on the national level. Two case studies at the local level strengthen the assessment. At the same time, we keep referencing to larger international developments to maintain a full picture.

Drucker (1985:17) already wrote that ‘innovation is the specific tool of entrepreneurs, the means by which they exploit change as an opportunity for a different business or service. It is capable of being presented as a discipline, capable of being learned, capable of being practiced’. Following these assessments, Porter wrote in his formative study on competitiveness that ‘a nation’s competitiveness depends on the capacity of its industry to innovate and upgrade. Companies gain advantage against the world’s best competitors because of pressure and challenge. They benefit from having strong domestic rivals, aggressive home-based suppliers, and demanding local customers’ (Porter 1990:73). In addition, Porter argued that the key elements for a nation to succeed and gain competitive advantage are based on factors conditions, demand conditions, firm strategy, structure and rivalry, and related and supporting industries (Porter 1990:86). Especially impactful was Porter’s Diamond Model of National Advantage which explains how certain companies from certain nations were capable to consistently lead in innovation. Using this model, Porter explained that nations succeed in industries where they are particularly good at factor creation. He also argued that when companies face competitive

disadvantage, like high land costs or labor shortages, they must innovate to advance and upgrade. Nations gain competitive advantage in industries where the home demand gives their companies a clearer and earlier picture of emerging buyer needs, and where demanding buyers pressure companies to innovate faster and achieve more sophisticated competitive advantages than foreign rivals. The third element of national advantage is the presence of related and supporting industries, which is based in the delivery of the most cost-effective inputs in an efficient, early, rapid and sometimes preferential way. Lastly, in the Diamond Model the firm strategy, structure and rivalry are factors based on strong tendencies of how companies are created, organized and managed. Competitiveness in a specific industry and the management and organization practices explain how countries differ in the goals that are seek to achieve.

As argued in Porter, a nation does not inherit but creates a factor of production to support its competitive advantage. **In this thesis, we aim to research whether nations could bring to cities the necessary capacity of effective and resilient energy policies to fight the global climate crisis through innovation. We thus analyze what are the states' energy policies for climate change at the national level, if they are following the guidelines of institutional frameworks and how these are applied on the city level.** For this reason, we take into consideration Porter's Diamond Model of National Advantage and the diamond as a system. Porter's Diamond consists of four factors that represent the key elements for a nation to succeed and gain competitive advantage over others. The diamond-shaped framework is fundamental for our hypothesis which tries to explain why one of the discussed energy industries is competitive internationally, whereas the other one might not yet be. Through Porter's model, we look at two urban case studies which, broadly perceived, could also create impact as models of green cities at national and international levels. **In order to provide a set of relevant policy frames to structure our analysis, we provide three important components of energy policy based on the institutional enforcement of policies combating climate change: climate action, energy efficiency and renewable energies.** A theoretical framework is created with the Porter's hypothesis on national competitiveness and innovation as an input, and as output the creation of cost-efficiency and resilient as well as a transnational model of green and environmental city. In order to analyze these case studies, we developed a framework that shows how through Porter's ideas and with institutional enforcements, cities can become more economic and sustainable:

Figure 2: Theoretical framework at the core of the thesis.

Dameri and Cocchia (2013) argued for the need to recognize that a combination of investment in society, urban infrastructure and rational management is required to promote economic development through actions and commitment from community members. Similarly, Porter's Diamond not only looks at the factors mentioned above but also the relation at the governmental level as well as it is taking into account the chance of natural disasters or random event. Porter thus underlined that shifting process of economic development vary from a static government towards a more collaborative process involving the government, companies, teaching and research institutions, private sector, organizations and more (Porter 1990). In particular, Porter's view on national competitiveness is based on the capacity of companies to achieve high levels of productivity. That way, green energy infrastructure and resources, energy efficiency, and mitigation on climate change, such as reducing CO₂ emissions from public services, would sustain altogether productivity growth. Moreover, the economy would need to upgrade itself towards innovation and green development energies.

We agree that international environmental regulations in a well-designed institutional framework could motivate cities and local industries to become more innovative and enhance competitiveness in a certain industry. This framework could provide flexibility, incentives and freedom to those industries in a community that need improvement on environmental and economic development. 'If correct this approach would lead cities and local industries to achieve better environmental and or better business performance and this enhance competitiveness' (Huang-Lachmann & Lovett, 2016:37). By looking how the two chosen cities plan and implement their climate change strategies, we expect to see how those institutional frameworks have been applied, implemented, renewed, or improved. Thus, we aim to examine whether these institutional frameworks could encourage synergy of economic competitiveness, social responsibility and environmental sustainability.

3. Research Methodology

A methodology of qualitative analysis has been adopted for the two case studies, as most of the data collected is gained from reviewing official statistics and related reports. In order to understand the city level, first we have analyzed both Germany's and China's energy landscape based on their main national climate policies strategies. Secondly, a general overview has been undertaken of both countries in their (a) energy mix during the year 2019; (b) Greenhouses Gas (hereafter: GHG) emissions and energy used by different sectors between 1960-2018 and of the implications of these trends continuing to 2020 and 2030; and (c) renewable energy sources and investment capacities. Thirdly, in the discussion part, a deeper analysis of the city structures of both Freiburg and Suining is presented. We have chosen Freiburg and Suining as urban case studies because (1) both cities follow a sustainable model of green investment; (2) both have similar location and build-up characteristics; and (3) both cities are possible green models of reference to replicate nationally and internationally. In terms of global recognition, both cities have won awards due to their commitment to protecting climate change: Freiburg the Germany's Federal Capital for Climate Protection sign in 2010 (GC 2018) and Suining the Global Green City award in 2012 (Suining Intensive Website Group 2019). Both cases are suitable to study and analyze their policies as well as to compare in large scale and capacity projects. We will use a qualitative approach to test whether Porter's hypothesis of national competitiveness and driven innovation could explain the cities green energy development models.

As we focus on the period from 1990-2019, our data collected is based on order of preference to recency and relevancy. The evidence and data analyzed is based on reviews of historical data, and extensively supported by close-reading relevant policies and primary sources such as government data, press releases, and reports by institutional organizations. We also draw from secondary sources, such as online journals, newspapers articles, academic journals and scientific books which are both based on recency and relevancy of the information. Such a combination of data types can be highly synergistic, as argued by Eisenhardt (1989:538), 'quantitative evidence can indicate relationships that may not be salient to the researcher. And qualitative data is useful for understanding the rationale or theory which can be strengthened.'. All used sources are written in Chinese, German, or English. Typically, in two case studies, researchers can combine qualitative and quantitative data. In this thesis, we chose mostly to use qualitative data based on a comparison of climate change institutional frameworks, national and local green policies. However, we also use quantitative data to assess the percentage or level of

development of the green policies at the national level, according to the following key indicators: share of energy mix, the number of emissions, green energy generation, and renewable energy consumption as a primary source.

As Pettigrew (1990) noted, ‘given the limited number of cases that can be studied, it makes more sense to choose cases such as extreme situations and polar types in which the process of interest is transparently observable’. Germany and China have been chosen as cases for comparison due to several reasons: Germany, as a leading member of the EU and the fourth-largest economy in the world, and China, in its capacity as an upcoming superpower and the second-largest economy in the world, are both blocs aiming to become global leaders in renewable energies. The EU aims to become a pioneer in achieving carbon-neutrality by 2050. China is already the world’s leading country in renewable energies production. Both countries are also relevant and interrelated to the global governance contributing to climate policies and negotiations (e.g., Davos 2020, COP 21, Paris Agreement, UN Agenda 2030, and more). Thirdly, Germany is in the top three countries in the world by total renewable power capacity, occupying the third position after China in the leading position, and the United States second (REN21 2019:187). Not least, it is of our interest, as part of the comparative advanced mater’s program at the University of Zurich, to conduct a qualitative analysis of green energy policies between both countries. Our analysis is thus relevant because we analyze how both countries, in general and on a local level, are competitive or not, and how they are adapting to the ongoing climate crisis.

This being a group effort, we have divided our individual research by regions of preference; yet we have also contributed mutually to all parts and contributed throughout. As many other, we have also faced unexpected limitations in our research as the global coronavirus outbreak has limited our possibilities of communication, impacted our access to sources and libraries, and we were not able to participate in seminars and events as planned. Still, this novel situation has encouraged us to do more online research and engage in video conferences. We have taken the opportunity to participate in webinars and gathered online-available data to find valuable and efficient sources to use in our research.

The facts and figures of our master’s thesis were crosschecked with official statistics in federal and municipal repositories to confirm their accuracy. We have collected data from the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, and Nuclear Safety (Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und nukleare Sicherheit, hereafter: BMU) as well as the German governmental working group on energy balance (Arbeitsgemeinschaft Energiebilanzen, hereafter: AGEB). AGEb evaluates current statistics and related data from all

areas of the energy industry and draws energy balance sheets for the Federal Republic of Germany every year and makes them available online. Data has also been collected from the German Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt, hereafter: UBA), Germany's main environmental protection agency since 1974. We also used data from the International Renewable Energy Agency (hereafter: IRENA), an intergovernmental organization that aims to facilitate, promote, and advance knowledge about the sustainable use of renewable energies. Finally, to acquire additional evidence, we have collected data policies and regulations from the International Energy Agency (hereafter: IEA). The agency's primary goal is to open new renewable energy sources to major emerging countries.

Chinese relevant sources were analyzed and collected from the main Chinese Communist Party News Website (*Guangming Daily* 光明日报), from the General Office of the State (国务院办公厅) and the National Development and Reform Commission (国家发展改革委, hereafter: NDRC). The NDRC is the state planning and development commission of the People's Republic of China (hereafter: PRC). It is a macroeconomic agency under the responsibility of the State Council (i.e. the Chinese government) and has central control over the administrative and planning agenda of the economy of China. We also used data from the National Energy Administration (国家能源委员会, hereafter: NEA), the state administration of the NDRC. The NEA mostly drafts China's national energy strategy and policies. The Ministry of Housing and Urban-Rural Development (中华人民共和国住房和城乡建设部, hereafter: MOHURD) provides housing and regulates the state construction of major urban projects in China; data from it has been useful too. We also consulted numerous other sources, such as data from China Petroleum News Center (中国石油天然气股份有限公司, hereafter: CNPC), China's largest oil and gas producer and supplier; and the Xinhua News Agency and China Report Net, both official state news agencies.

4. Energy Policies within Two Systems: Germany and China in Comparison

The aim of this part is to analyze Germany's and China's national energy policies; to see what are their different visions and targets for renewable energies; and to review their approaches to energy efficiency and climate action practices. We will describe and analyze what are the implementations in the short and in the long term. Finally, an overview of the local implications and practices that have been applied in the two cities chosen as case studies of our research is presented.

4.1. National-level Energy Policies in Germany

As a member of the EU, Germany's climate policy is guided by the framework of EU energy and climate policies: the climate and energy package (EU 20-20-20), the Single Energy Market, the EU emissions trading system (EU ETS), and the 2030 new energy and climate policy framework (IEA 2020) are all of relevance at the national level too. The EU strategy for new energy and climate framework for 2030 is divided into three main areas: emissions mitigations, boosting renewable energy, and deepening energy efficiency. Germany's international commitment to climate change is based on the Paris Convention on Climate Change and UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) on clean energy and climate action. German national strategies in energy policy are based on large financial transfers and participation in research and innovation funding programs from the European Framework Program H2020. Moreover, the German Federal State plays an active role in multilateral organizations, forums and initiatives, e.g. within the G7 and G20 frameworks, IRENA, IEA, UN's Sustainable Energy for All (SE4All) initiative, Mission Innovation, the Africa-EU Energy Partnership (AEEP), the Renewable Energy Policy Network for the 21st Century (REN21), the Clean Energy Ministerial (CEM) and the World Bank's Energy Sector Management Assistance Program (ESMAP) (Kuittinen & Velte 2018:36).

In addition to all these international commitments to mitigate climate change, the German State and all of the 16 German administrative regions proposed a joint initiative named *Energiewende*—the Energy Transition—in 2010. The initiative defines Germany's energy policy landscape for the present and future. It is an energy and climate change initiative introduced by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie, hereafter: BMWi). The objectives of the *Energiewende* are aligned and

supporting the EU's energy and climate policies, the Paris climate agreement, and UN Sustainable development goals. The initiative involves all government levels, including several ministries and public administrative bodies, as well as business communities and society. The BMWi also coordinates the dialogue with other relevant stakeholders. This is expected to create a high level of transparency, contributing to a more significant public acceptance of the energy transition. The ministry also exchanges information between the energy transition platforms. The five energy transition platforms are energy grids, electricity market, energy efficiency, building, and research and innovation. They are essential for the dialogue between the ministry and stakeholders (Kuittinen & Velte 2018:11).

The Energiewende, being the major plan for transforming the country's energy system to make it more efficient and supplied mainly by renewable sources, has been long in the coming (Kuittinen & Velte 2018:19). The first time the term was used was in the 1980s, when an institute near Wyhl, 30km away of the Rhine River in Southern Germany and not very far away from Freiburg, created the first study of German Energy Transition. The town was the chosen home a new nuclear reactor. However, back in 1975, local farmers and students forced the government to abandon its plans, and this became the first time the construction of a nuclear reactor was stopped in Germany (Kunzig 2015). The town became synonymous with a successful civil involvement into the national energy policy ever since.

The Energiewende aims to move Germany towards a low carbon and nuclear-free energy system by the middle of the century (IEA 2020). In recent decades Germany has shifted from a clear dominance on coal and oil industry towards more renewables usages. Although even today, coal represents the largest source of energy, it is planned to phase out by 2038 (IEA 2020). The Energiewende is a long-term national strategy that addresses all sectors of the economy and it is framed by two key policy documents, the Renewable Energy Act (EEA) and the Energy Concept (Kuittinen & Velte 2018:19). The EEA went signed into law in the year 2000 and the Energy Concept was adopted in 2010; additionally, after the Fukushima nuclear disaster in 2011, Chancellor Merkel's administration decided to phase out nuclear energy production by 2022. The EEA and the Energy Concept are the two most important climate protection tools that drive renewables' growth in Germany.

Germany is seen internationally as one of the pioneer countries in the development and application of Renewable Energy Sources (RES). A few main aspects to highlight are:

- Germany's substantial increase in renewable energy share by 40.1% in 2019;
- Germany progressive phase-out of nuclear power by 2022;

- Germany is the leading wind energy producer in Europe with a total capacity of 59.3 GW in February 2019;
- Germany's fourth global position in photovoltaic (PV) capacity but world-leading position in PV capacity per capita;
- Germany's fourth position in bio-power generation and fifth position in capacity (with China in the world-leading position).

(Sources: AG-Energy Balances 2019; REN21 2019)

The current high standing of Germany in green energy matters could not have been achieved without political, economic and technological development (Quitow et al. 2016). Since the UNFCCC was adopted in 1992, members and countries reunited again at the 21. session of the Conference of the Parties (COP21) in Paris in December 2015. Each nation agreed on submit its own Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDC). Germany was the pioneer country in positioning itself with a policy framework, Klimaschutzplan 2050—the Climate Protection Plan 2050. The plan aims at meeting the goals of the Paris Agreement and was approved in November 2016. Klimaschutzplan 2050 collects principles and goals of the climate protection policies of the German government. It provides a transparent process to achieve domestic climate targets in line with the Paris Agreement. The key areas of action are energy, buildings, transport, trade and industry, agriculture and forestry, and the primary key measures are:

- Long-term targets: based on the principle of extensive greenhouse gas neutrality in 2050;
- Guiding principles und transformative pathways for all areas of action by 2050;
- Milestones and targets for all sectors up to 2030;
- Strategic measures for every area of work;
- Establishment of a learning process that enables the progressive raising of ambition envisaged in the Paris Agreement.

(Source: BMU 2016)

As of 2019, Germany had reduced its total GHG emissions by around 35.7 % compared with 1990, bellow the set target of 40% reduction (see figure 3). Germany would need to reduce its GHG by 56% by 2030 to fulfill its National Policies from the Klimaschutzplan 2050 (Appunn, Eriksen & Wetterngel 2020). Hence, Germany has to find new policies and measures that will help reaching the national GHG emissions objectives for 2020 and 2050.

Germany's greenhouse gas emissions 1850-2018 and reduction targets

(Source: Appunn, Eriksen & Wetterngel 2020)

Figure 3: Germany's greenhouse gas emissions 1850 – 2018 and reduction targets

Additionally, the country needs to reduce emissions in the energy power sector. For this is the sector responsible for the most significant greenhouse gas emissions: a great majority of the total emissions come from the energy sector; this has been the case for over 150 years already (Appunn, Eriksen & Wetterngel 2020). Germany also needs to expand and prepare new policies and measures for reducing in large scale the GHG emissions in transportation and heating sectors. Thus, the German government created in March 2019 a cabinet-climate to provide a new package of emissions reduction to meet by 2030. This new package had a set of new carbon pricing systems which aimed to lower fees on electricity prices for households and companies by providing tax relief.

Still, Germany is struggling to achieve climate change goals. In September 2019, the German government adopted Klimaschutzplan 2030, which includes a carbon price system in the transport and heating sectors. The Klimaschutzplan 2030 aims to help the country to meet climate change goals by 2030. Some of the main aspects of this new climate package are:

- Confirmation that Germany will phase out coal energy by 2038;

- A goal to turn 7-10 million electric cars on the road powered by 1 million charging points;
- A goal to increase the renewables share of power energy to 65% by 2030;
- Revision of the current climate cabinet and carrying out annual reviews of climate objectives—the government will institutionalize a body that will assign and monitor the progress on legally-binding reduction emissions targets per sector;
- Reduction of the impact of higher carbon prices on commuters and low-income householders: people driving to work will thereby be able to claim 35¢ per km of commuting (up from 30¢ per km) until the end of 2026.

(Source: Federal Government 2019)

This more short-term plan also is mindful of the distribution of the impacts of climate policies across sectors and stakeholders. Both policies and regulations can help Germany to achieve cost-efficiency, equitable and sustainable pathway as part of the energy transition. The government aims at greater expansion of renewables as a positive effect for the national grid; however, it still needs to phase out the consumption of nuclear and coal fossil fuels. Thus, it has set improvements to taxation and market regulation for the distribution of infrastructure, improvement and functionality of the renewables integration system as the primary goals.

4.1.1. Germany’s Green Energy Overview

In the following table, we have summarized the key quantitative targets of the Energiewende and arranged them according to energy efficiency, renewable energy, and climate action targets for Germany. We will use this table as a reference for analyzing whether Freiburg follows the same targets.

Energy efficiency	2020	2030	2040	2050
Greenhouse gas emissions (from 1990) – long-term climate neutral	-40%	55%	-70%	-80% to 95%
Primary energy consumption (from 2008)	-20%			-50%
Electricity consumption (from 2008)	-10%			-25%
Energy demand in buildings (from 2008)				-80%
Energy consumption in transport (from 2005)	-10%			-40%
Heat demand in buildings (from 2008)	-20%			

Renewable energies (RE)	2020	2030	2040	2050
RE share in final energy consumption	18%	30%	45%	60%
RE share in electricity consumption	35%	65%		>80%
RE share in transport	10%			
RE share in heating	14%			

Climate Action by sectors	Energy	Buildings	Transport	Industry	Agriculture
Klimaschutzplan 2050 Climate Action Plan 2050					
Reduction of GHG by 2030 by sectors (from 1990)	- 62% to 61%	- 67% to 66%	- 42% to 40%	- 51% to 49%	- 34% to 31%

Klimaschutzprogramm 2030 Climate Protection program 2030	2020	2021	2025	2026	2030
CO2-pricing scheme		10 EUR /ton		35 – 60 EUR/ton	35 EUR/ton
Increase price of diesel fuel		3 cl/liter	10cl/liter		
Renewable energy levy (EEG-levy) – up to 10% decrease in 2023		-0.25 ct/kWt			
expansion offshore wind energy	15GW				20GW
Federal Support for Efficiency Buildings (BEG) – exchange premium for renewable heat of hybrid	Exchange premium 40% costs cover	Exchange premium 40% costs cover	Exchange premium 40% costs cover	Prohibition oil fired heating systems	
EV incentives with a price below 40.000EUR					7 to 10 million EV
Rail prices reduction					-19% to 7%
Freight transport – commuter allowance price increase			>21km 35 ct/km		
Reduce Greenhouse gas emissions (from 1990)					-55%

(Source: our compilation of data collected from the German Federal Government 2019.)

Table 1: Germany’s Green Energy Overview.

In the Climate Action Plan 2050 it is stated that three main measures are of key importance: first, reduction GHG emissions by 80%-95% at the national level; secondly, increase the share of renewable energy sources by 60%; thirdly, increase the renewables in the final energy consumption by 80% by 2050. To assess this progress, we analyzed in the following sections the role of renewable energies in the energy mix in Germany, the number of gas emissions generated by the sector, and the share of solar and wind sources in the country according to the Klimaschutzplan 2050, and the Klimaschutzplan 2030.

4.1.2. Energy Mix 2019

Germany’s power mix share of renewable energy sources takes about 40.1% of the total production (Appunn, Haas & Wetterngel 2020). Regardless, there is a surplus of gross consumption of renewables that positions Germany in a positive balance in the power export of RES. Significantly, in the 2010 Energy Concept, the country aimed for renewables to account for 35% gross electricity consumption (in the power sector) by 2020; by 2018 Germany already

overreached with 38% and 44% in the first half of 2019 (IEA 2020, see figure 4). Initially, the government agreed to increase the share of renewables in electricity generation by 80% by 2050. But seeing already a positive surplus, the government is planning to reach a share of 65% in renewable electricity by 2030 (Eckert 2019).

(Source: Appunn, Haas & Wetterngel 2020)

Figure 4: Renewables' share in gross power consumption 2019

So far, renewable energies have mostly supplied the electricity sector. By contrast, heating and transportation sectors' share of renewables is still relatively low. As shown in figure 5, the share of RES in electricity reached about 38% of the total, leaving for the heat and cooling about 14% and 6% in transport (as for 2019) (Renewable Energies Agency 2019). Thus, Germany's renewable energy expansion shows its ambitious plans, because the country has already demonstrated to the world that a 30% share of renewable energy is possible (IRENA 2015). However, to fight climate change, become energy-efficient, sustainable, and a low carbon economy, Germany also needs to expand its focus beyond the power sector, and address further challenges in the transport and heating sectors.

Share of renewable energy in Germany's final energy consumption 1990–2018

(Source: Renewable Energies Agency 2019)

Figure 5: Renewables' share in gross power consumption 2019

4.1.3. GHG Emissions

Greenhouse gas emissions are produced by several sectors in the German economy, such as households, trade and commerce, industry, and transportation. Although the tax on CO₂ is increasing in the long run, it is still very low (UBA 2019). According to a 2019 emissions projects report by the BMU, Germany is set to widely miss its goal to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 40% by 2020. However, a press release from the AGEB confirmed in March 2020 that primary energy consumption decreased about 2% in comparison to the previous year (AGEB 2020). According to the AGEB, energy consumption in Germany in 2019 peaked at 12.32 petajoules (PJ), which translates into 437.8 million tons of coal equivalent. In a report written by Nagl et al. (2011), the authors concluded that Germany's energy policy scenarios are adopting challenging climate targets to reach the national targets in the electricity sector by 2050. The power system needs to change from fossil fuels to renewables-based energy sources, but the scholars also confirmed that it would be possible to have a gas reduction of up to 95% set by 2050 (Nagl, et al. 2011). However, other authors strongly criticized the German model on the energy transition. Quitzow et al. (2016:165) compared the Energiewende to 'a risky endeavor, a climate disaster, an economic failure, a burden for consumers and industry, and also called it technologically outdated'.

Despite the efforts of Germany to decrease the consumption of primary sources of energy, the IEA warned that ‘urgent action is needed to all fronts’ (DW 2018). In 2018, the IEA announced that there had been an increase in global CO₂ emissions despite the intention to continue fighting global warming. Mostly, the CO₂ emissions increased in China (2.5 %), the USA (3.1 %), and India (4.5 %), but in Europe emissions fell by 1.3 %. Germany still contributes to air pollution on a large scale—mostly emitting nitrogen and dioxide pollutants—mainly due to the significant dependence on the country’s vehicle industry. Most of the cars are and were manufactured with diesel combustion. As part of the Klimaschutzplan 2030, the government is implementing a carbon price for transport emissions which would raise fuel prices. Recently, with the support of the National Platform Future of Mobility (NPM), the government has announced an increase on prices for the fuel and promoted EVs, cycling, public transport, rail and all short of vehicles that would reduce in the short and long term the gas emissions. It remains to be seen what effects these policies will have in the long run.

4.1.4. Share of solar and wind renewable energy sources

According to AGEB (2020), there is almost 15% of renewable energy that is used as primary consumption. There has also been an increase of 8% in the total of renewables from 2018 to 2019, especially in solar and wind energy technologies (AGEE- Statistics 2019). Germany’s production of solar and wind energy is divided by north and southern regions. Notably, wind power is collected in northern Germany and solar power in the southern regions. Although there was an increase in solar and wind generated power, networks that connect the north to the south are not yet stable and enough developed. Thus, there are delays in grid expansion, as demand continues to increase from the industrial and metropolitan areas (IEA 2020).

Figure 6 shows a map of Germany with a division on solar and wind energy capacities. The fact that the northern federal states have surpluses of power generation and southern ones are having deficits creates an imbalance in the energy consumption. Moreover, the government is also addressing the impact of the onshore wind sector as the growth is still deficient compared to other RES, and it is characterized by ‘aged’ wind facilities. That would explain the government’s priorities to expand the grid operators and infrastructure. Public opposition has also appeared in recent years, while the government tried to reach out to solutions to help meet emissions targets. By increasing solar and wind energy power generation and capacity there will surely be a decrease in fossil fuel consumption (Kunzig 2015). As mentioned above, the main drivers for Germany’s change of policy were not only climate protection and environmental sustainability, but also the reduction of energy imports, high tech development

and economic growth (Quitow et al. 2016). By minimizing the external dependency from Russia and other EU countries, Germany has made advancements on research, development, and deployment of future energy systems to secure energy efficiency and supply. Many authors support the idea of regional and local governments to rely on each other more in relation to renewable energy technologies as a means to reduce the external dependency, and therefore to strengthen local value creation and secure improvement of jobs (Rave & Albrecht-Saavedra 2015; Leibenath, Wirth & Lintz 2016).

(Source: Kunzig 2015)

Figure 6: Solar and wind energy in Germany – Installed capacity by postal code area megawatts per square mile, 2014 – 2050

4.1.5. Local Energy Policies in Freiburg

Freiburg is a city located in the south-western region of Baden Württemberg in Germany, at the edge of the Black Forest and between France and Switzerland. It has around 220 000 inhabitants (as of 2013), but the population growth rate is 2.51 % per year, so it is expected that in 2020 the population would reach 262 000 inhabitants (Population city 2020). Since 1970, Freiburg city has tackled energy and climate change issues in a very integrated way, and as well the city has developed efficient transport and land use, and developed democratic values among citizens. In order to aggregate the city policies towards urban sustainability, acquiring new experiences and skills the city created a Sustainable Management unit in 2011. It was directly managed by Freiburg Sustainable Council which was set up by the Municipal Council in 2009 to meet the climate future challenges. The city was honored with Germany's Federal Capital for Climate Protection sign in 2010, and the German Sustainability Award in 2012, presented for the first time to towns and cities, as the most sustainable city in Germany (GC 2018). The city is building a green profile for the future for its leading solar industrialization, high-quality life and nature conservation (Thomas 2012). Gregory (2011) describes Freiburg as a Green City as it excels in areas of energy, waste management, land conservation, and green economies.

The city also invests money in to research and creates jobs that encourage environmental protection. Freiburg's ecosystem and the city's improvements in human behavior ensures people and land working together toward a better and greener economy. Thanks to the green economy Freiburg's community is devoted to contribute to local resources, waste management, and apply policy learning processes that encourage stakeholders to be active in promoting local renewable energies. As described by the former mayor Dieter Salomon, Freiburg has become the European Union's 'Solar Valley' (City of Freiburg n.d.). The city provides economic benefits to its citizens by creating a hub of technical expertise on the solar technology industry. Citizens have also been very involved in the development of the communal facilities that in the long term can produce electricity power from renewable energies. The goal is to bring social benefits from the green energy industry. In terms of environmental scope, besides the creation of new jobs that are employed in green economy, the university also offers specialized international masters degrees on renewable energy management disciplines which promotes the environmental value too.

4.2. National-level Energy Policies in China

China's attention to the international deployment of renewable energy investments and emission reduction is of great importance to the development of its energy industry. Since its adhesion to the World Trade Organization (WTO) in 2001, the Chinese economy has undergone several economic reforms and has established its position on the international community's global environmental obligations. Before China's commitment to the Paris agreement, the country had already engaged in bilateral negotiations on climate change and clean energy with Germany, the UK, France, India, and the USA (Li 2016). During each East Asia Summit (EAS), the ASEAN countries—Australia, China, India, Japan, New Zealand, the Republic of Korea, the USA and Russia—meet to discuss new ways of decarbonization, energy efficiency, and other green policy research activities (ASEAN 2019). East Asian countries have the fastest growing rate of carbon dioxide emission in the world, and it is expected to continue to grow. During the Paris Climate Summit in 2015 Xie Zhenhua, China's chief negotiator confirmed the interest and commitment for China in a transition to low carbon development and to resolve the issue of funding technology transfers (Li 2016). To better promote the new energy technology innovation among the EAS countries, the International Cooperation Department of the Ministry of Science and Technology made three recommendations: first, to follow the framework of the BRI to promote regional scientific and technological innovation cooperation. Second, China is willing to continue sharing know-how and experts for deeper developing green energy solutions. Third, to combine the Yunnan region's successful practices and achievements in green energy, low carbon development, and climate change (Technology Daily 2019).

Given the partially planned-economy nature of the PRC, every five years the central government makes plans and implements them economically, politically, culturally, socially, and environmentally. The country is preparing for more considerable efforts to increase environmental awareness, eliminate pollution, and prevent significant risks and poverty (Guangming Daily 2019). We have collected the central policies undertaken by China to transform the traditional energy structure towards renewable sources, efficient energy, as well as pollution control to protect climate change. In what follows, we summarize these central policies from the 11th, 12th, and 13th Five-Year Plans (FYPs) as well as from additional environmental strategies.

During the 11th FYP (2006-2010) the General Office of the State Council adopted numerous central environmental protection policies. First was to implement annual target management of the main tasks and indicators of environmental protection. Secondly, to develop a circular

economy along a coordinated development of the environment and the economy. Thirdly, to increase investment in environmental protection, where governments at all levels should include environmental protection as a key content of financial expenditure. Fourth, to strengthen environmental protection supervision at the national, local, and unit levels of responsibility, to improve regulatory guidance and to implement environmental protection laws and regulations. Fifth, to enhance public participation for major construction projects. Sixth, it was to develop the environmental protection industry by improving the technical level of protection equipment and establishing mechanisms for pollution control facilities. Seventh, to expand international environmental cooperation exchanges and participation in international conventions and related trade and environmental negotiations (General Office of the State 2006).

The subsequent 12th FYP (2011-2015) had considerable attention to energy and combating climate change. Some policies were aligned to the status quo, but other aspects had more ambitious goals to reduce fossil energy consumption, promote low-carbon energy resources, and restructure China's economy. The main targets were:

- A 16 % reduction in energy intensity (energy consumption per unit in GDP);
- To increase non-fossil energy to 11.4 % of total energy use;
- A 17 %reduction in carbon intensity (carbon emissions per unit DGP).

(Source: State Council 2013)

The relationship between energy and economic growth in China matters; without a reduction in energy intensity since the late 1970s, the country would need to consume three times the energy it does today to sustain its intensity growth (Lewis 2011). The 12th FYP provided a preview of China's leadership on new energy and climate program plan to move the country forward. The plan itself offered a framework for progress but left details to implement for policymakers. The proportion of coal in primary energy consumption was envisioned to drop from 70% in 2009 to about 63% in 2015. The percentage of electricity consumption from natural gas, hydropower, nuclear energy and other non-fossil energy sources (mainly wind, solar and biomass) were to increase respectively 3.9%, 7.5% and 0.8% to 8.3%, 9%, and 2.6%. (China Economic Net 2010). Optimizing the energy consumption structure had also become one of the goals of the central government. Yet, the country was and still is facing ongoing pollution challenges.

The following and current 13th FYP (2016-2020) went a step further towards tackling the ongoing climate crisis. The National Development and Reform Commission (hereafter NDRC)

and the National Energy Administration (NEA) announced in January 2017 that part of the 13th FYP would also be a guideline for making an ‘energy revolution’ in China, highlighting the following:

- An increase of renewable power capacity to 680 GW by 2020;
- An increase of the share of non-fossil energy in total primary energy consumption to 15% by 2020 and 20% by 2030;
- Increase installed wind capacity to 210 GW;
- Promote offshore wind and ocean power development;
- Lead renewable energy technology innovation;
- Further support the development of the renewable energy industry in China and decrease reliance on foreign companies in the domain;
- Resolve renewable power curtailment issue problem.

(Source: IEA/IRENA Renewables Policies Database 2018)

The current FYP aims to offer quantifiable short-term goals for limiting coal in favor of oil and gas to cut emissions. It promotes renewable energy development, aims to improve energy industry efficiency, and encourages technological solutions for a greener future. The plan proposes that the total energy consumption should be stopped at 4.8 billion tons of coal by 2020. To achieve these goals, clean and low-carbon development is needed as is an optimization of the energy structure and changes of priorities for the country’s energy development. There will also be a group of large-scale hydropower and nuclear energy projects to start construction or to complete installation by 2020. Green energy, such as wind energy and solar energy, will continue to develop steadily. The main goals during the 13FYP are:

- Non-fossil energy consumption increase should be more than 15%;
- Natural gas consumption should reach 10%;
- The proportion of coal consumption fell below 58%.

(Source: Energy Bureau 2017.)

In November 2014 the State Council issued a new Strategic Action Plan for Energy Development for 2014-2020 (能源发展战略行动计划 2014-2020 年). This Action Plan is divided into three parts: overall strategy, strategic policy and objectives, and safeguard measures of the annual energy development up to 2020. The plan’s main tasks are to enhance the independency on energy guarantee capability, to advance the energy consumption

revolution, to optimize the energy structure, to expand energy cooperation, and to promote energy innovation. The plan also emphasizes China's strategic goals in 2020 as follows: 'It is further necessary to reform the energy system, improve and improve energy policies and all departments and regions must do a good job on the organization, implementation, supervision, and inspection' (Xinhua News 2014). The overall strategy of the plan is thus to create an upgraded version of China's energy system and provide a safe and reliable energy guarantee. It includes the following objectives:

- Saving strategy: By 2020, the total primary energy consumption is to be controlled at 4.8 billion tons of standard coal, and about 4.2 billion tons for the total coal consumption.
- National strategy: By 2020, a relatively complete energy security system will be basically formed. The energy self-sufficiency shall remain at around 85%, the oil reserve-production ratio increases to 14-15, and the energy reserve emergency system will be basically completed.
- Green and low-carbon strategy: By 2020, non-fossil energy source will account for 15% of primary energy consumption, natural gas will account for more than 10%, and coal consumption will be controlled at 62%.
- Innovation-driven strategy: By 2020, China should form a unified, open, and orderly modern energy market system.

(Source: State Council 2014.)

The main measures of the Action Plan are settled around its strategic objectives. Its specific contents include the following items:

- To enhance the capability of energy self-sufficiency it promoted the development and usage of coal, clean, and efficient energy. It has also developed natural gas and alternative energies.
- To promote energy consumption revolution, it has controlled the growth of energy consumption, focused on implementing energy efficiency plans, and improved urban and rural energy transfer of energy supply methods.
- To optimize the energy structure, it has reduced the proportion of coal consumption and increased the percentage of natural gas consumption. It has also kept the development of nuclear energy safely.
- To expand international energy cooperation, it has called for building BRI projects that actively support the energy technology, equipment and engineering teams abroad.
- To promote energy technology innovation, it has clarified the strategic direction and focus of green energy technology innovation. It relied on significant projects to drive

the self-innovated technology of green energy innovation, accelerating the construction of the technology innovation system.

- To develop a more profound reform of the energy system to ensure national energy security it has established a unified, open, and modern energy system, as well as promote an energy price reform.
- To improve and perfect the energy policy it has improved the energy tax policy by accelerating the change of taxes and fees and gradually expanding the scope of resource tax of high energy-consuming and highly polluting products.
- To do a good job in organization and implementation it has strengthened the organizational leadership of the National Energy Commission and related organs.

(Source: State Council 2014.)

However, as China still implements economic stimulus policies, the stop to carbon emissions will not come very soon. Another policy implemented to combat the growing emissions was the Energy Production and Consumption Revolution Strategy 2016-2030 (能源生产和消费革命战略 2016-2030 年) proposed by the NDRC and NEA in December 2016. The document put forward measures to ‘promote the energy consumption revolution and create a new situation of energy saving and efficiency’ (NDRC 2016). It also called for the production of a mid-to-high level energy consumption structure, promoting energy-saving and emission reduction. The Chinese leaders see the importance of establishing and implementing the new development concept. The main priorities are to take the idea of the energy revolution as a national policy for energy development. The country is building a foundation for energy security, promoting the consumption of energy supply, and strengthening cooperation to achieve a fundamental change in energy production and consumption patterns in the years up to 2030.

Yet, from the perspective of the implementation of those policies, governments, and enterprises have different priorities. At the enterprise level, to implement environmental protection policies is relatively complex. For small and medium-sized enterprises, the development of environmental protection in industries can lead to government tax relief and policy support—such as the development of water-saving and sewage treatment systems in certain areas can bring forth tax-free subsidies. At the same time, some large enterprises assume environmental responsibility and aim to help the country complete the environmental protection goals. For example, in May 2010 Alibaba Group announced that it will allocate 0.3% of the group’s annual revenue as a public welfare fund mainly for environmental protection. It was the first environmental protection fund for domestic internet companies (Alibaba Group 2010). Alipay, which belongs to Alibaba Group, introduced in August 2016 a digital initiative named

Ant Forest that aimed at encouraging users to convert their shopping income into tree planting behavior (UNEP, 2019). With this program, eight new protected areas have been opened in China having a positive impact on a number of desert ecosystems. In September 2019, Ant Forest project was awarded by the UN Earth Guardian Award (UNEP 2019).

4.2.1. China's Green Energy Overview

China's green energy structure, as it is most commonly so, is divided into renewable energy and non-renewable energy sources. In recent years, China's environmental problems have attracted worldwide attention, primarily the phenomenon of smog and water pollution. These environmental problems not only damage the health of the Chinese people, but have also slowed down the sustainable development of the economy. To solve these problems, the government has been trying to change the energy structure and energy utilization by significantly reducing the use of coal, and developing clean energy such as hydropower and nuclear energy power. China has already become the leading country for clean energy investment worldwide (China Report Net 2018).

In the following table, we have collected the key goals and targets of the Chinese energy transition structure accounting renewable sources, efficient energy, and two main policies addressed to protect climate change.

Energy efficiency	2020	2030
Greenhouse gas emissions GHG (from 2005)	- 40% to 45%	- 60% to 65%
Non-fossil energy accounts for total primary energy consumption (from 2013)	15%	20%

Renewable energies (RE)	2020	2030
Non-fossil energy	15%	20%
Natural gas	10%	15%
Coal consumption	58%	49%

Climate Action	2020	2030
能源生产和消费革命战略 Energy Production and Consumption Revolution Strategy (2016-2030)		
Total energy consumption	5 billion tons of standard coal	
CO2 emissions per unit of GDP (from 2015)	- 18%	
Energy consumption per unit of GDP (from 2015)	- 15%	
Unit value-added power consumption of industrial enterprises	- 10%	

Natural gas		15%
Non-fossil energy		20%
Average coal consumption of power supply	300g to 310g standard coal/kWh	

“十三五”时期能源发展主要指标 Main indicators of energy development during the "13th Five-Year Plan" period						
category	category	unit	2015	2020	Average annual growth	Attributes
Total energy	Primary energy production	100 million tons of standard coal	36.2	40	2.0%	Anticipation
	Total installed power	Gigawatt	15.3	20	5.5%	Anticipation
	Total energy consumption	100 million tons of standard coal	43	<50	<3%	Anticipation
	Total coal consumption	100 million tons of raw coal	39.6	41	0.7%	Anticipation
	Electricity consumption of the whole society	Trillion kwh	5.69	6.8-7.2	3.6-4.8%	Anticipation
Energy security	Self-sufficient rate	%	84	>80		Anticipation
Energy structure	Installed proportion of non-fossil energy	%	35	39	(4)	Anticipation
	Proportion of non-fossil energy power generation	%	27	31	(4)	Anticipation
	Proportion of non-fossil energy consumption	%	12	15	(3)	Binding
	Proportion of natural gas consumption	%	5.9	10	(4.1)	Anticipation
	Proportion of coal consumption	%	64	58	(-6)	Binding
	Proportion of electric coal in coal consumption	%	49	55	(6)	Anticipation
Energy efficiency	Energy consumption reduction rate per unit of GDP	%	-	-	(15)	Binding
	Coal consumption for power supply of coal-fired generating unit	Gram standard coal/kwh	318	<310		Binding
	Power line loss rate	%	6.64	<6.5		Anticipation
Environmental Protection	Reduction rate of carbon dioxide emissions per unit of GDP	%	-	-	(18)	Binding

(Source: our compilation of data collected from China Economic Net 2016; Dong 2019.)

Table 2: China's Green Energy Overview

4.2.2. China's energy consumption structure 2017, 2018

In general, non-renewable energy sources such as coal (59%) and petroleum (18.8%) account for nearly 80% of energy consumption, while green energy still accounts for a relatively low proportion. The main reason is the country's heavy dependence on coal: China's coal reserves are plentiful, and the primary distribution industries have started to form based on coal. Additionally, the heavily developed petroleum industry owns a large amount of oil land reserves, such as the country's largest Daqing Oil Field. After the reform and opening up in the 1980s, China has rapidly developed its petroleum industry with such conglomerates as PetroChina, Sinopec and other large state-owned enterprises. China's crude oil imports were ranked first in the world, and the future is predictable: China will further optimize its energy structure and reduce its dependence on foreign crude oil (CNPC 2019). Finally, due to historical and political reasons, the share of green energy in China's energy consumption is still meager. But at the same time, the air pollution problems have severely damaged the health of the Chinese people. Due to the waste emissions from the use of crude oil and coal, China's sulfur dioxide emissions are also stable among the top three. To reverse these situations, China has introduced various measures to develop green energy while improving the consumption of non-renewable energy.

4.2.3. GHG emissions

As mentioned above, China is the country with the highest carbon emissions in the world. Although the intensity of carbon emissions in China has declined to a certain extent in recent years, the overall carbon emissions have been rising. In figure 7 we can see how the Chinese CO₂ emissions are dominated by coal. Together with the USA, it has become the country with the most significant carbon emissions in the world (Peters, Andrew & Korsbakken 2019). 'China had projected to be responsible for effectively all the increase in global CO₂ emissions in 2019, with a rise of 0.26GtCO₂, as for gigatons of CO₂,—larger than the global total increase of 0.24GtCO₂' (Hausfather 2019). Since China's current energy structure is still dominated by the use of fossil energy (oil, coal), the share of green energy in China's energy consumption is still very low. The Chinese government meets almost every year to discuss the issue of levying carbon emission taxes, but so far, no carbon emission taxes have been imposed. What is certain is that China's carbon emissions will continue to increase in the coming years. China had promised in 2015 that China would reach the peak of carbon dioxide emissions by 2030, and China would strive to reach its height as soon as possible (SCIO 2015). China has also pledged that the carbon dioxide emissions of its unit GDP in 2021-2030 will be 60% to 65% lower than

in 2005. In the future, China’s carbon dioxide curve will continue to rise, but, according to more hopeful estimates, it may become flattered and reach its peak in 2030.

(Source: Peters, Andrew & Korsbakken 2019)

Figure 7: Chinese CO₂ emissions by source, 1960-2018

4.2.4. Share of nuclear and hydropower energy sources

Nuclear energy and water energy are energy sources that do not produce pollution or waste. In terms of nuclear energy, by 2020 China’s total nuclear power generation will exceed that of non-APEC countries. From 1990 to 2020, China’s nuclear power generation has leaped from 0 to 400 TWh. The development rate is faster than the growth rate of nuclear power generation in OECD countries. From 2020 to 2040, China’s nuclear power generation capacity will increase significantly, and may even exceed the total of nuclear power generation in APEC countries. China is committed to the safe development of nuclear power. The country has the world’s most advanced nuclear technology at military and industrial levels, as well as the world’s most advanced nuclear reactor technology. Geographically, China has a large amount of land suitable for the construction of nuclear power plants.

In terms of hydropower, China’s hydropower generation growth has surpassed all other countries from 2005 to 2017 (Dudley 2019). After the Three Gorges Dam project, China

continued to develop hydropower resources in the northwest and southwest regions. China's goal is for the scale of conventional hydropower to reach 340 million KW by 2020, and the new constructions under the 13th FYP will add over 60 million KW (NDRC 2016). Depending on the low season and high season and geographical location, hydropower will undertake the role of regulation and delivery RES during the 13th FYP period to help China better meet the seasonal supply of energy. China plans to build many large-scale, high-investment hydropower nuclear power projects from 2016 to 2020.

4.2.5. Local Energy Policies in Suining

Suining city is located in the middle of the south-central Sichuan Basin, and the middle reaches of the Minjiang River. It is bordered by Chengdu in the west, Chongqing in the south, Nanchong in the east, Mianyang in the north. It is the political, economic, and cultural center of central Sichuan. In 2002, Suining had a population of 658 798; however, it grew to 3 629 000 by 2019 (Baikē.baidu.com n.d.). Known as the 'little Chengdu', in 1985 Suining was chosen by the State Council to establish a prefecture-level city with jurisdiction over multiple counties and smaller towns in the region. There are currently 112 towns and 2097 administrative villages, covering an area of 5300 square kilometers which make up the municipality. The region is rich in natural gas and brine resources, with proven natural gas reserves of 35 billion cubic meters and salt brine reserves of 4.2 billion tons (MOHURD 2009). Due to its convenient transportation network, Suining is increasingly becoming the second largest transportation hub in Sichuan Province (Suining News Network 2018).

Although Suining is close to Chengdu and Chongqing, Suining's economy is still at the low point of Sichuan's economic development (Du 2018). The gap between urban and rural areas is large, and the development of towns and villages lags behind. Since 2008, the economic growth rate of Suining is higher than the average for Sichuan, and it is in a state of catching up. Still, the problems of a sizeable urban-rural gap and insufficient coordination of urban and rural development are outstanding. In 2014, the per capita disposable income of urban residents was 22790 RMB. The income per capita of rural residents is only 9482 RMB, only 41% of the disposable income of urban residents. In the past ten years, although the income of both urban and rural residents has increased, the gap between urban and non-urban residents is significantly wide (Du 2018).

Urban infrastructure construction also lags behind. With the rapid growth in the last years, the construction of infrastructure in Suining has been unable to meet the needs of further urban development. Suining is a city located in a hilly area. The area is relatively narrow, the cost of

widening is high, the space of urban roads is insufficient, and traffic congestion is an issue. In the process of urbanization construction, water conservancy facilities such as water resources storage, water cleaning, and flood prevention are lacking. Although several rivers pass through the urban area, the limited water quality guarantee capacity results in low water resources affluence. Simultaneously, the sewage treatment capacity is weak, and many areas have not been able to achieve rain and sewage diversion, which affects the overall urban water environment. The treatment of urban garbage also needs to be improved. In 2014, the city's domestic garbage disposal rate was 91.98%, while Sichuan Province has reached 97.24%. The construction of public green space is backward, and the problem of the lack of parks and plazas in many towns and villages has not been resolved (Du 2018). In 2014, the water penetration rate and gas penetration rate of urban residents in Suining were 82.66% and 82.25% respectively—8.46% and 8.64% lower than the overall level of Sichuan Province. The province's per capita park green area and green coverage rate in the built-up area reached 11.26 m and 37.51%, 3.02 m, and 4.02% higher than that of Suining city.

5. Discussion: Differences and Similarities in Green Energy Policies

In the following parts we want to analyze how cities have adapted federal and national institutional frameworks and develop a cluster of national competitiveness and technological development, towards energy efficiency, renewable energies and climate action targets that would lead to social, environmental and economic changes. The analysis of the two cities is thus aiming to test whether Freiburg and Suining conform to our proposed theoretical framework as a representation of a green city model, including the social, economic and environmentally sustainable model. We also aim to test if Porter's Diamond Theory of National Advantage can be used for gaining additional insights.

5.1. Case Study of Freiburg

Freiburg has developed since 1970s a model of green energy and green economy for sustainable development that is especially noteworthy according to many authors (Thomas 2012; Gregory 2011). In terms of renewable energies, Freiburg has a large capacity for solar, wind, hydropower, and biomass sources of production. Solar energy power is by far the most visible renewable resource in the city, and biomass is the largest share of Freiburg's renewable electricity generation. The Black Forest provides a wide supply of wood. Through innovative new techniques, Freiburg private and city-owned waste management companies are improving its recycling and energy efficiency through efficient technologies in combined heat and power (CHP). CHP produces both electricity and heat by capturing the waste heat from electricity to generate more electricity and useful heat: 'The increase in CHP's share from 3% to 50% has enabled Freiburg to reduce its reliance on nuclear power from 60% to 30%--and provides local heating at the same time' (Gregory 2011). Freiburg's location of being surrounded by the deep forest and having a sunny climate compared to other cities in Germany has attracted many tourists and pro-climate groups and individuals who enjoy the relaxed pace of life in the city. Although Freiburg's climate is recognized as mountainous continental, without reaching extreme ups and downs in temperature it allows the region to have a stable consumption of energy sources. Usually, the warmest months are in June and July. Also, in these two summer months most of the sunlight is collected, reaching up to 8 hours per day. Additionally, Freiburg is an inner-city. Therefore, lack of western winds from the coastline has allowed it to create an ecosystem that develops the full potential of solar energy industry through photovoltaic solar

panels. Through educational programs, networking associations, and information programs, the local government is creating an impact on the local people, tourism, and businesses to promote climate protection and knowledge of energy-saving opportunities, intending to create awareness as a part of the regional energy strategy.

Freiburg has collected the best of German infrastructure and skills in the field that has allowed companies to develop the maximum potential in solar energy and biomass waste sources of renewables. According to Porter (1995:57), ‘the competitive advantage of a location does not usually arise in isolated companies but in clusters of companies—in other words, in companies that are in the same industry or otherwise linked together through customer, supplier, or similar relationships’. In figure 8 below we can see the city’s approaches and institutions aimed at contributing to the formation of the Green City Cluster in Freiburg. Among them are: wind power plants, education and training centers, eco-farming, bioenergy and sustainable waste utilization, green communications, green economy, energy-saving and climate protection, public transport, green spaces, green living and more. The Green City Cluster’s activities contribute to better positioning the city on international markets for products and services in the areas of renewables and solar energy, energy efficiency, sustainable building and planning, as well as environmental technologies (Green City Cluster n.d.).

(Source: Green City Cluster n.d.)

Figure 8: Freiburg Green City Cluster

We have found various reasons for the public institutions and companies to become strategically competitive in green terms. The creation of a cluster in the city responds to Porter's argument that a city can become competitive in an industry where all sectors, including firms, industries, resources, and tools are aligned together. There is a handful of public and private institutions that are working together to develop the cluster and to promote citizenship engagement on green sustainability in Freiburg. First, it is the city itself. Thanks to its strategies of restricting the use of cars in the city, providing effective transport alternatives to the car, and regulating land use to enable public transport, cycling and walking, the city actively contributes to lower CO₂ emissions. Related is Badenova, the green energy supplier for the city of Freiburg that promotes and supports strategic new opportunities for companies and individuals to enable renewable energies projects. The company also uses its Innovation Fund for Climate and Water protection to support pilot projects that otherwise would not be pursued due to their lack of profitability. Research institutes are also part of fundamentals of the cluster. One example is the Fraunhofer Institute of Solar Energies Systems provides innovative solutions, new concepts, and pilot projects for companies and develops sustainable energy systems for those who are interested. Finally, private companies also contribute to the development of the Green City Cluster. An example can be Aiforia, an agency for sustainability that provides solutions on the local and regional level, such as management of natural resources or the interlinkages between urban and rural activities. Freiburg Future Lab, a virtual mobile lab that boosts projects related to green development, is another one. It aims to show the part of the track towards sustainability by offering training programs and visits related to the subject of urban development and energy supply.

The Green City Cluster in Freiburg has taken around 70 measures of climate protection to seek energy balance on renewable energy use by local companies. The four primary areas of action are mobility and transport, energy efficiency and energy management, expansion of renewable energies and public relations, and green networking (Green City Cluster n.d.). Thanks to this cluster, the city has gathered benefits such as better air quality, quiet transport, space efficiency where pedestrian can reach any part of the city in walking distance, and the possibility to power its transportation with clean, renewable energy. Additionally, Freiburg's land areas are given two-thirds of the total land to green uses. Forests take up 42%, while 27% is used for agriculture, recreation, and water protection. (Thomas 2012). Moreover, Freiburg's geography and climate are favorable, but also the population's awareness has helped the city to promote itself as a model green city due to direct citizens' participation, dynamic planning, and consensus. Since the successful blockage of the nuclear plant construction in the 1970s, 'the

most committed leaders [of the anti-nuclear movement] joined the political arena, the administration, the utilities, found a job in educational or research activities or founded green-spirited companies' (Energie-Cites 1999).

Apart from the Cluster Initiative, Freiburg began to develop the Dietenbach district in the neighborhood of Rieselfeld in western parts of the city. The district is to become a climate neutral area with short distances, accessible day care centers, shopping opportunities, open spaces, schools and sport facilities. The detailed outline is under construction, and citizens are having the opportunity to contribute and to give suggestions for the city structure planning. The municipality should have a final structural and planning of the project by December 2020 (City of Freiburg, n.d. (b)).

The Freiburg Environmental and Renewable Energy Business Network, another local green initiative, collects research institutions, international companies, as well as trade firms, suppliers and service providers, all of which are pushing toward an alternative to fossil fuels consumption (GC 2018). The network has developed many innovative and green projects. For example, the Green City Tower, a 48m-high residential and commercial block, is a green lighthouse project that generates much of its power from solar energy and saves all the excess of energy in a large lithium-ion battery.

Another example of the green city policies is the University of Freiburg, which since the publication of the University's environmental policy in June 2007, has followed an environmental policy towards becoming carbon neutral. This was further supported when the Innovation Charter was launched in July 2011, with the objective to work together to make Freiburg the green center of education, science, technology innovation and businesses. In 2015, the renewed University of Freiburg library was opened to the public becoming one of the largest and most modern university libraries in Europe, with more than half of reduction on energy consumption in heating, power and water (Uni-Freiburg 2018). The library utilizes a whole range of modern green technologies to earn its title of a truly sustainable building: ground water is used for cooling and heating; smart lights adapt the light temperature according to daytime and the rooftop is layered with solar panels.

Freiburg's main two goals are to become carbon neutral by 2050 and to become a 100% renewable energy region by 2035 (Go100% n.d.). Related studies have proven that a region empowered by 100% renewable energy can be achieved by 2050 (GC 2018). Comparing to the national targets, already after the UNFCCC of the COP 21 Freiburg has positioned itself as a city ready to act for climate protection. The city uses renewable energy strategies such as 'go green' as a way to attract workers, tourists, and companies thereby aims to stimulate the local

economy (Gregory 2011). Freiburg also has partial ownership over local energy supply or distribution. The Land Value Capture (LVC) is ‘an approach used to help finance new infrastructure projects by harvesting a portion of the increase in value of nearby property caused by this investment’ (REN21-REC 2019:101). LVC is often used to help fund major transport infrastructure projects. Similarly, Freiburg is known for developing an extensive regional public transportation system, especially supporting bicycling. The city’s capacity to invest or reallocate budgets in renewable energy projects by collecting taxes, fees and other levies has also been adapted widely.

All this confirms our hypothesis that Freiburg is a leading example of energy efficiency and renewable energy growth. It also provides evidence to what Porter described in this model, namely that a nation needs key factors to succeed on national competitiveness. In this case the city has a mix of factors conditions, e.g. infrastructure, skilled labor and innovation techniques, demand conditions, e.g. market growth rate and saturation, firm strategy, structure and rivalry, and related and supporting industries that allow the city to succeed and gain competitive advantage amongst others. The Green City Cluster feasibility study additionally proves that Freiburg is on path to become fully renewable and this will create regional value creation, technology transfer and global marketing. According to city officials, some EUR 3 billion in investment funds is needed for renewable energies and some EUR 12 billion for building renovation. As also laid out in Porter’s model, boosting the local economy will have a win-win impact on the national economy and therefore add to the national competitiveness. The solar industry in Freiburg employs over 2000 people in 100 companies—three to four time the national average. As we learn from Porter, the regional consolidation of the solar industry will become a national competition that will influence its future development.

5.2. Case Study of Suining

As aforementioned, Suining is located in Sichuan Province and is thus an inland city (see figure 9). As such, it is geographically relatively far away from China’s economically developed Pearl River Delta and Yangtze River Delta regions, and politically far away from China's political center, Beijing. It can collaborate with developed cities to accelerate superior industries in Sichuan Province, e.g., new energy industries and green manufacturing, and succeed in those sectors after the transfer of core technologies to developed cities. In the Sichuan Basin, there is much rain and not so much sunlight. The terrain is complex, which is not suitable for the development of the solar energy industry. However, due to the many rivers and related water

bodies, the region has been developing hydropower energy sources. Suining Municipal Government is also actively developing tourism. Rivers are passing through the city center of Suining, and technical resources are nearly sufficient to achieve green and sustainable development. The city's climate is characterized as subtropical humid with regular monsoons.

(Source: SCSNTV 2019.)

Figure 9: Suining City

In China, generally speaking, the government environmental protection policies are implemented first at national level. After setting those targets, the government assigns tasks to state-owned and private enterprises, giving them administrative and guidance support. However, in large cities, the government focus leads towards economic goals, whether in small cities, the government focuses on ecological goals and citizens' commitment. That is why many small cities in China have received the Green City Award rather than large cities (Suining Intensive Website Group 2019). Since the establishment of the Global Green City Goal in 2012, Suining has formulated five major paths based on the green city assessment standards towards natural ecology, green population, sustainable economy and society, green residential system, and green public transportation (Suining Intensive Website Group). Nominations for a range of related awards—such as the National Innovation City, National Ecological City, UN Habitat Environmental Award, International Garden City, and Global Green City—can be seen as proof that the city has had a global impact and has been recognized as a global green city (Suining

Intensive Website Group). There are six major green development goals underlying the sustainable policies of the city. We will discuss each of them shortly in what follows.

Sustainable urban planning is the first goal. In the blueprint, the city government controls the planning of the central city (except the old city) and the individual planning of water, electricity, sponge city construction, and other special construction plans, as well as the town master plan's revision. In addition to the preparation of plans, Suining city also ensures the unity of the local plans and the consistency of planning and implementation through a planning supervision mechanism (Du 2018). Related is the plan of a green urban informatization. The city government of Suining hopes to gradually build a new model that relies on the development of the Internet and invest a lot of money to strengthen the construction of the information field. At present, Suining has established an urban public information platform and is constructing a geospatial information platform; the basic urban database is constructing a geospatial database. A smart construction project was created, where the digital management coverage for the urban construction projects helped the construction of the city's housing information system and the integrated urban development management platform. Initially, a new underground pipeline management information system was established. Through the smart health project, the city also developed a county regional health information platform and completed the construction of the private health network, covering more than 95% of the health institutions, and 80% of the third-level hospitals in the city passed the digital hospital acceptance (Du 2018).

The third goal is that of water ecology. The municipal government tries its best to improve urban water ecology and strictly manage water resources. Suining first strengthened ecological protection for municipal water systems. The urban blue line and green line were delineated, and management measures were formulated separately. Strict penalties were imposed for arbitrary occupation and destruction of the environment. The city also called for ecological restoration of the original but damaged water system of the city. Along the Guanyin Lake, Suining city has built Shenglian Island, Wetland Park, Lianli Park, and Xiwu Erzhou Wetland Park. These parks are rich in environmental assets and make full use of the wetland water purification function to carry out the original hard flood control. Ecological restoration can effectively control urban sewage discharge and protect the water quality of the Fujiang River. Finally, it is to strengthen water pollution prevention. A comprehensive water quality test and pollution source investigation was conducted on the tributaries of the Fujiang River passing through the city. A water quality guarantee plan and plan were formulated. In the end, the city wants to ensure the quality of drinking water sources (Du 2018).

Forth comes the goal of creating a ‘Sponge City’—that is, to utilize most modern urbanistic technologies to capture and re-use rain water and to help prevent flooding. Suining actively applied for national financial subsidy funds and increased local government financial input. In 2015, the city allocated RMB 100 million from local debt to re-finance funds as a special fund for sponge city construction. In addition, the Agricultural Development Bank also granted a billion-dollar loan to Suining city. Government support and enterprise operations are useful models for the long-term maintenance of many public facilities. Suining encourages sponge city-related project construction and development units to adopt the Public-private partnership (PPP) model for construction and the Engineering, Procurement and Construction (EPC) model for operation and maintenance, which attracts social capital to build sponge cities. The total investment of the project is RMB 2.526 billion, and the prospective term of completion is in ten years (Du 2018).

The fifth goal is pollution control. Suining has introduced strict access standards to prevent the construction of industrial systems in high-pollution and high-emission industries. The city strictly controls high-energy-consumption and high-pollution industries, limiting the total number of major pollutants. An environmental impact assessment of the expansion project is carried out regularly too. New projects must be reported to the municipal counterpart in advance. The city government has gradually tightened the credit supply to environmentally destructive and overcapacity industries. Suining has also developed a mechanism for linking new projects in high-energy-consumption and high-pollution industries to the progress of energy-saving and emission-reduction targets. For industrial projects with an annual comprehensive energy consumption of over 5000 tons of standard coal and a yearly production of over 100 tons of COD (chemical oxygen demand, e.g. pesticides and metals) the government and enterprises must submit a written report to the leading municipal group on climate change and energy conservation to ensure emission reduction. Specific measures to eliminate corresponding backward production capacity are proposed as well (Du 2018).

The sixth and final goal of Suining’s green policies is related to technological innovation on climate change and renewable energies. Since traditional technological innovation is guided by a single value goal, promoting economic development also brings about environmental degradation. Today, global warming, water pollution, and flood disasters have become the main global environmental problems. However, the deterioration of the environment has further compressed the space of economic growth and significantly weakened the motivation of technological innovation. The government of Suining has thus gradually realized that it is difficult to achieve sustainable economic development without protecting the environmental

resources, and it has successively formulated a large number of corresponding innovative technologies to protect the environment (Du 2018).

5.3. Main Differences

In terms of climate change recognition, actions are based on low-carbon concepts, rational planning, and the usage of appropriate technology. The differences between our two chosen cases arise firstly from national differences. On one hand, Germany is not only updating its plans and promoting technology research but is also consolidating and developing further low-carbon concepts. These lead to the achievement of sustainable lifestyles, consumption, and production models. China, as a developing country, is still assessing what should be changed to promote climate change and sustainable development locally. Renewable energy technology is a new way of technological development. China's global renewable energy investment has increased, and major breakthroughs have been made in related technical fields. However, China's and Germany's routes towards renewable energy and traditional fossil energy have had different trajectories. China recognizes renewable energies sources as natural gas, hydropower, nuclear energy as main sources, and non-fossil energy sources such as wind, solar and biomass as secondary ones. However, Germany's recognition of renewable energy sources is based on wind power, solar photovoltaic power generation, biomass energy and geothermal energy.

According to Porter, 'a nation will export those goods that make the most use of the factors with which it is relatively well endowed' (Porter 1990:79). Similarly, Freiburg has created its most important factors of production, such as skilled human resources and scientific base of the energy industry, its export materials. Freiburg's specialization in the solar energy industry is oriented to satisfy the city's needs; therefore, it gains competitive advantage among other regions. On the other hand, Suining's recent green innovation is mainly due to domestic demand and central pressure to innovate. Public state companies in Suining still lead their actions to sustain a commitment to the industry. In the case of Freiburg, the green energy cluster offers and supports a network of public institutions, companies, and citizens that are supporting each other towards a common goal of international competition, high specialization, and cost-effectiveness. Additionally, Freiburg is the city that hosts many of the major trade fairs related to international environmental industries. In contrast, Suining's efforts for R&D work and its goals to accelerate the pace of innovation, resolve around boosting competition between factories, industries, companies in the same local ecosystem.

Furthermore, the Innovation Charter in Freiburg creates an opportunity for companies, industries, and factories to influence, exchange, and provide a mix of ideas and information to accelerate innovation in the solar industry. However, as for Suining, the city is acting on behalf of the municipality and the national energy administration of the NDRC, thereby, there is a strong rivalry that also encourages the creation and persistence of competitive advantage. Especially, the development in the city is based on four industries: electronic information; food and beverage, chemical energy industry, and advanced material e.g., lithium battery materials (Sichuan Online 2018). The fact that Freiburg is a multi-award-winning city, starting by being awarded the title of an Eco-Capital in 1987 (GC 2018) has already created a process of dynamism economic and sustainable approach for decades. On the other hand, since 2012 when Suining received the Global Green City award, Suining is seeking to build a strong foundation and popular public support for environmental protection of its new energy industry. Yet, it is at the starting point of a full adaptation of green policies. Finally, the weather conditions are different in both cities. Freiburg has a great capacity of producing solar energy and has done so for many years already. By contrast, Suining is just developing the new energy industry. It will also have the advantage of creating an ecosystem based on hydropower energy rather than solar energy.

In sum, Freiburg has an established and thriving Green City Cluster. There is an umbrella of associations related to the green energy industry and a business network community that allows the region to decide and to become more expert at the federal level, and therefore provide impulse to the German green energy industry to grow competitive internationally. On the other hand, Suining is supervised and monitored on the implementation and control of green energy policies by the central government and sometimes municipal bodies of experts that aim to bring new tools for technological development, technicians' skills, research guidance, and improvements for the private sector. Yet, other than Freiburg, Suining is just starting its green energy trajectory. Chinese energy agencies and central bodies in charge of the national energy policies have reliable power to influence locally what potentially could modify or formulate city's policies according to the city needs and national goals. Freiburg is an example of a green city energy model as it is starting to transform Germany's national *Energiewende* from bottom up—actions of a local government impact all sectors of society. Suining is also an example of a green city. But, Suining promotes the implementation of green policies at the local level through the adaptation of national strategies in a top-down manner. Hence, the city of Suining does not support the economic ground for green development from our triple sustainable model as much so as Freiburg does.

5.4. Main Similarities

Porter described how a model of competitiveness in a specific industry is reflected by how a given city is formed by its institutions, enterprises, and technology development, and how the companies, institutions, government, and citizens are merged in collaborating for a more efficient and well-managed policy regulation (Porter 1990). The low-carbon transformation has become a significant challenge faced by governments, enterprises, and societies of many countries. Among them, Germany's goals to become carbon neutral by 2050 shows the development and application of low-carbon technologies, which promote low-carbon innovation projects and new usages for clean energy sources. Similarly, China's investment in science and technology to deal with climate change has been large, and has lasted for many years too. Most of the technical research on climate change has been focused on the mechanism of low-carbon technological innovation to mitigate climate change. We found that the response of low-carbon technological innovation to climate change is vaguely visible in Suining. However, nationally the research of the technological environmental protection is important for evaluating the effect of low-carbon technology innovation and clarifying the future direction and goals. Since the early 2000s, China has increasingly realized the importance of the threat of climate change, and its scientific and technological efforts to curb climate-warming have also been strengthened. Low-carbon technological innovation is a meaningful way to cope with climate change, and it is also a "win-win" plan to solve economic and environmental problems.

Many of these issues became visible on the local level in our research. Freiburg has been adapting its policies from the federal level and has proved that the local economy has a stronger impact than the national level. The city has built a green energy ecosystem that aims to achieve climate neutrality and 100% renewable input by 2050, way above the percentage of 80-95 % goal from the central federal government. Suining also received primary support and supervision to implement their policies by the central government. Having performed many ground innovations on low-carbon strategies and technologies, e.g., energy performance, green buildings and urban renewables, Suining can create models that could escalate to other Chinese provinces and even internationally. As for the national level, China aims to reduce coal consumption by 58% in 2020, and plans to increase the non-fossil energy consumption up to 15%. Yet these numbers are very challenging for the size of the country and the developing capacity in technological, research and infrastructures projects. It remains to be seen whether Suining might have an influence on these changes.

Freiburg's energy supply strategy is based on three pillars of energy saving, efficiency, and renewable sources. The local authorities have already built up climate protection to these goals by 2007. As described above, by 2030 the city aims to reduce CO₂ emissions by at least 50 % and in the long term to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. Suining municipality, following the national energy administration strategy plan, has also clarified specific measures to improve the energy structure. The pillars here are as follows: 'saving, clean and safe' strategic policy as well as an acceleration of the construction of clean, efficient, and safe energy. The goal to become climate neutral can only be achieved by reducing the energy consumption per capita and increasing energy efficiency in the private and commercial sector. At the same time, the goal to become fully renewable can only be achieved by working together with the surrounding districts and industries. In both cases, the cities have adopted technology for renewable energy. Through technological innovation, the respective local governments try to solve the restrictive problems of the technical field. Using new technologies also has excellent professional competitiveness and long-term technical advantages. It has a significant potential for cost reduction. It can compete with traditional techniques and occupy a large market share as it has a rapid expansion of the scale of technology development while the cost drops sharply.

All this is confirming our hypothesis that only when there are synergies of similar enterprises in a city that work together, technological development and innovation key for a city to be a green model can come forth. That also proves that having a fundamental climate policy framework, whether at the state, federal, or at the international level, that supports the energy transformation is vital to adapt and transform a city towards being climate-friendly. Despite both cities following two different types of governance models for climate adaptation planning, both face the similar problems due to externalities of financial markets and climate governance. The private sector, local communities and municipalities do not have sufficient incentives to participate in combating climate change. Although the UN and many countries around the world have adopted mitigation measures and technologies to fight climate change, the cost of developing new technologies is very high. The government needs to provide a large amount of continuous financial support to technological innovation in renewable energy.

6. Conclusion

The findings of the discussions presented in our thesis confirm the initial hypothesis that nations can become more competitive through new ways of innovation in the green energy industry. As the analysis through the prism of Porter's Model has also made visible, cities can acquire a more inclusive green model thanks to national competitiveness and innovation-driven techniques. We have also observed that both cities follow different political strategies on green energies, but both have created local demand and sufficient resources and factor conditions to develop a green energy ecosystem. They also face common challenges, such as lack of green urbanizations, cheap, and effective renewable energy sources. As a possible recommendation, we encourage that cities create synergies and partnerships between each other, where they can face to face prioritize challenges and learn from each other's experiences. For instance, Chinese' sustainable urbanization efficiency model can be replicable to other cities, while European green models of cities could also lead to business opportunities, possible technological exchanges, and more. The main goal ought to be to mitigate climate change by creating long-lasting cooperation relationships between cities and nations. Porter stated that where there are synergies of critical industries that are working towards the same goal, technology development and innovation naturally come together. Accordingly, we conclude with the assertion that cities globally can become more competitive towards the energy transition by stimulating R&D, innovation, and technological development of renewable energies.

Both Freiburg and Suining are examples of global cities that can potentially become partners in sustainability models. China's national conditions and policies on green energy are different from the ones of Germany and those at the EU level. Existing research at the European level has focused on the attributes and laws of low-carbon innovation and its role in mitigating climate change. In the same way, China's central government has coordinated and evaluated to many local governments its plans to combat climate change. But at the municipal level the evaluation of technology is still imperfect and the application process needs to be standardized. Biermann et al. have argued (2009) that where there is a process of global environmental governance at the macro or micro levels fragmented systems have become very common. Both Germany and China emerged in the recent years as global leaders in green policies, a tendency only advanced further by the withdrawal from the Paris Agreement in 2017 by the USA. China especially sees this as a huge opportunity to become a responsible country in terms of the environment nationally and to establish its image as a trustworthy country towards the world (Liu 2008).

Green technologies have been increasing and growing faster and faster. Thus, innovation matters not only at the level of enterprise but increasingly for global economic growth. European member states, the PRC, and other nations are still afraid of losing competitiveness in global markets due to implementing radical change needed for a safer climate for future generations. However, in most cases, countries that become innovation leaders in specific popular sectors outperform their rivals in revenue growth, profits, and share of price performance—a statement only further underlined when taken into account the stable high position of Germany, and the rising position of China, in Bloomberg’s Innovation Index, (Jamrisko & Lu 2020). Young (1991) emphasized that developed countries should take the lead in reducing emissions and providing more financial and technical assistance to developing countries. In terms of environmental issues, China strives to improve itself and hopes to be a leader in green policies in the future, while still facing difficulties in technological and industrial transformation. The EU sees China's primary goal as to become a superpower nation. However, the EU and China should unify their financial capacities, support each other and provide knowledge and skills to transfer to those who need assistance, especially in terms of looking forward to having a united and robust alliance to mitigate climate change.

7. References

- AGEB, 2020, *Arbeitsgemeinschaft Energiebilanzen legt Bericht zum Energieverbrauch 2019 [Working Group on Energy Balances presents report on energy consumption from 2019]*, viewed April 13, 2020, from https://ag-energiebilanzen.de/index.php?article_id=29&fileName=ageb_pressedienst_02_2020.pdf.
- AGEE-Stat, [AGEE-Statistics], 2019, *Schätzung zur Entwicklung der erneuerbaren Energien im Jahr 2019 [Estimation of the development of renewable energies in 2019]*, viewed 10 April 2020, from https://ag-energiebilanzen.de/#20191217_agee-stat_praesentation_pev_ee_2019.
- Alibaba Group, 2010, *Alibaba Group earmarks 0.3 percent of annual revenue for conservation of environment*, viewed 13 June 2020, from https://www.alibabagroup.com/en/news/press_pdf/p100514.pdf.
- Appunn, K., Eriksen, F., & Wetterngel, J., 2020, 'Germany greenhouse gas emissions and climate targets', Cleanenergywire.org, viewed 7 April 2020, from <https://www.cleanenergywire.org/factsheets/germanys-greenhouse-gas-emissions-and-climate-targets>.
- Appunn, K., Haas, Y. & Wetterngel, J., 2020, 'Germany's energy consumption and power mix in charts', Cleanenergywire.org, viewed 7 April 2020, from <https://www.cleanenergywire.org/factsheets/germanys-energy-consumption-and-power-mix-charts>.
- ASEAN, 2019, *Chairman's statement of the 14th East Asia Summit*, viewed 14 June 2020, from <https://www.asean2019.go.th/en/news/chairmans-statement-of-the-14th-east-asia-summit/>.
- Baike.baidu.com, n.d., '遂宁 [Suining]', viewed 14 June 2020, from <https://baike.baidu.com/item/遂宁>.
- Basiago, A.D., 1996, 'The Search for the Sustainable City in 20th Century Urban Planning', *Environmentalist* 16, 135–155.
- Biermann, F., Pattberg, P., Van Asselt, H., & Zelli, F., 2010, 'The Fragmentation of Global Governance Architectures: A Framework for Analysis', *Global Environmental Politics* 9, 14-40.
- BMU, 2016, *Climate Action Plan 2050: Principles and goals of the German government's climate policy*, viewed 20 April 2020, from https://www.bmu.de/fileadmin/Daten_BMU/Download_PDF/Klimaschutz/klimaschutzplan_2050_kurz_f_en_bf.pdf.
- Bundesregierung [Federal Government], 2019, *Klimaschutzprogramm 2030 [The Climate Protection Program 2030]*, viewed 10 April 2020, from <https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-de/themen/klimaschutz/klimaschutzprogramm-2030-1673578>.
- Chen, J., 2019, 'Green investment definition', Investopedia.com, viewed 27 March 2020, from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/g/green-investing.asp>.
- City of Freiburg. n.d. (a)., *Freiburg Green City: Approaches to sustainability*, viewed 19 April 2020, from <https://fwtm.freiburg.de/pb/Lde/603024.html>.

- City of Freiburg. n.d. (b). *New district of Dietenbach*, viewed 20 April 2020, from <https://www.freiburg.de/pb/495838.html>.
- Dameri, R.P., & Cocchia, A., 2013, 'Smart city and digital city: twenty years of terminology evolution', *itAIS* 14, 1-8.
- Drucker, P.F., 1985, *Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, Butterworth-Heinemann, New York.
- Du, C., 2018, 'Way and Reference of Green Development of Suining in Sichuan', *Journal of Shenyang University of Technology* 11 (2), 105-111.
- Du, K., Lin, B., & Xie, C., 2017, 'Exploring Change in China's Carbon Intensity: A Decomposition Approach', *Sustainability* 9 (2), 1-14.
- Duch Guillot, J, 2019, 'The European Parliament declares climate emergency', [Europarl.europa.eu](http://europarl.europa.eu), viewed 18 February 2020, from <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20191121IPR67110/the-european-parliament-declares-climate-emergency>.
- Dudley, B., 2019, 'BP 世界能源展望' 2019 年版中文报告 [BP World Energy Outlook 2019 Chinese Report], [Bp.com](http://www.bp.com), viewed 20 May 2020, from https://www.bp.com/content/dam/bp/country-sites/zh_cn/china/home/reports/bp-energy-outlook/2019/2019eobook.pdf.
- DW, 2018, *Climate change: Energy-linked CO2 emissions hit record high in 2018*, viewed 13 April 2020, from <https://www.dw.com/en/climate-change-energy-linked-co2-emissions-hit-record-high-in-2018/a-48060649>.
- ECG, n.d., *The future we choose – An economy aligned with ethical values*, viewed 22 May 2020, from <https://www.ecogood.org/what-is-ecg/vision-and-values/>.
- Eckert, V., 2019, 'Germany needs to ease rules to hit 2030 renewables target', [Reuters.com](http://www.reuters.com), viewed 10 April 2020, from <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-germany-electricity-climate/germany-needs-to-ease-rules-to-hit-2030-renewables-target-idUSKCN1TJ20C>.
- Eisenhardt, K. M., 1989, 'Building Theories from Case Study Research', *Academy of Management Review* 14 (4), 532-550.
- Energie-Cites, 1999, *Thermal solar energy – Freiburg (Germany)*, viewed 20 April 2020, from <http://www.agores.org/>.
- EP, 2019, *Climate and environmental emergency, P9_TA (2019)0078*, viewed 15 February 2020, from https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2019-0078_EN.html.
- European Commission, 2007, *Communication from the Commission to the European Council and the European Parliament: An Energy Policy for Europe*, viewed 15 February 2020, from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52007DC0001>.
- GC, 2018, *Green City Freiburg, Management Marketing, FWTM*, viewed 15 May 2020, from <https://www.freiburg.de/greencity/index.html>.
- GII, 2018, *Energizing the World with Innovation*, viewed 30 May 2020, from <https://www.wipo.int/publications/en/details.jsp?id=4330>.
- GII, 2019, *Creating Healthy Lives — The Future of Medical Innovation*, viewed 30 May 2020, from <https://www.wipo.int/publications/en/details.jsp?id=4434>.
- Gippner, O., & Torney, D., 2017, 'Shifting Policy Priorities in EU-China Energy Relations: Implications for Chinese Energy Investments in Europe', *Energy Policy* 101, 649–658.
- Go 100% Renewable Energy, n.d., *Freiburg 100% renewable region*, viewed 29 May 2020, from

- [http://www.go100percent.org/cms/index.php?id=69&tx_ttnews\[tt_news\]=168&cHash=c5afc4d363d29e9b5ecff9f6f99bc03b](http://www.go100percent.org/cms/index.php?id=69&tx_ttnews[tt_news]=168&cHash=c5afc4d363d29e9b5ecff9f6f99bc03b).
- Green City Cluster, n.d., *Cluster Green City Freiburg*, viewed 18 April 2020, from <https://www.greencity-cluster.de/?L=1>.
- Green Impact, n.d., *Triple sustainability model*, viewed 23 May 2020, from <http://www.greenimpact.group.shef.ac.uk/wordpress/about/sussed/>.
- Gregory, R., 2011, 'Germany - Freiburg - Green City. The ecotipping points project – Models for success in a time of crisis', Ecotippingpoints.org, viewed 17 April 2020, from <http://www.ecotippingpoints.org/our-stories/indepth/germany-freiburg-sustainability-transportation-energy-green-economy.html>.
- Hausfather, Z., 2019, 'Analysis: Global fossil-fuel emissions up 0.6% in 2019 due to China', Carbonbrief.org, viewed 17 May 2020, from <https://www.carbonbrief.org/analysis-global-fossil-fuel-emissions-up-zero-point-six-per-cent-in-2019-due-to-china>.
- Hook, L., 2019, 'Climate change: how China moved from leader to laggard', Financial Times, viewed 28 January 2020, from <https://www.ft.com/content/be1250c6-0c4d-11ea-b2d6-9bf4d1957a67>.
- Huang-Lachmann, J.T., & Lovett, J.C., 2016, 'How Cities Prepare for Climate Change: Comparing Hamburg and Rotterdam', *Cities* 54, 36-44.
- IEA, 2017, *World energy report: A world transformation*, viewed 24 February 2020, from <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2017>.
- IEA, 2020, *Germany 2020: Energy policy review, country report*, viewed 3 April 2020, from <https://www.iea.org/reports/germany-2020>.
- IEA/IRENA Renewables Policies Database, 2018, 'China 13th Renewable Energy Development Five Year Plan (2016-2020)', IEA.org, viewed 10 May 2020, from <https://www.iea.org/policies/6277-china-13th-renewable-energy-development-five-year-plan-2016-2020?page=4§or=Multi-sector>.
- Investopedia, n.d., *Sustainable Investing*, viewed 30 March 2020, from <https://www.investopedia.com/sustainable-investing-4427774>.
- IRENA, 2015, *Germany has additional potential to increase use of renewables in heat and transport sectors*, viewed 14 April 2020, from <https://www.irena.org/newsroom/pressreleases/2015/Nov/Germany-Has-Additional-Potential-to-Increase-Use-of-Renewables-in-Heat-and-Transport-Sectors>.
- Isenhour, C., McDonogh, G., & Checker, M., 2015, *Sustainability in the global city: Myth and practice (new directions in sustainability and society)*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Jamrisco, M., & Lu, W., 2020, 'Germany breaks Korea's six-year streak as most innovative nation', Bloomberg Innovation Index, viewed 29 May 2020, from <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/articles/2020-01-18/germany-breaks-korea-s-six-year-streak-as-most-innovative-nation>.
- Kenton, W., 2019, 'Green tech definition', Investopedia.com, viewed 27 March 2020, from https://www.investopedia.com/terms/g/green_tech.asp.
- Kuittinen, H., & Velte, D., 2018, 'Case study report: Energiewende. mission-oriented R&I policies: In-depth case studies', European Commission, viewed 24 March 2020, from

- https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/mission_oriented_r_and_i_policies_case_study_report_energiewende-de.pdf.
- Kunzig, R., 2015, 'Germany could be a model for how we'll get power in the future', National Geography, viewed 6 April 2020, from <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/magazine/2015/11/germany-renewable-energy-revolution/>.
- Leibenath, M., Wirth, P., & Lintz, G. 2016, 'Just a Talking Shop? Informal Participatory Spatial Planning for Implementing State Wind Energy Targets in Germany', *Utilities Policy* 41, 206-213.
- Leopold, A., 1949, *A sand county almanac*, Oxford University Press, New York.
- Lewis, J., 2011, 'Energy and Climate Goals of China's 12th Five-Year Plan', Greengrowthknowledge.org, viewed 10 May 2020, from https://www.greengrowthknowledge.org/sites/default/files/downloads/resource/Energy_climate_goals_china_twelfth_five_year_plan_Pew.pdf.
- Li, A. H. F., 2016, 'Hopes of Limiting Global Warming? China and the Paris Agreement on Climate Change', China Perspectives, viewed 14 June 2020, from <https://journals.openedition.org/chinaperspectives/6924?file=10>.
- Nagl, S., Fürsch, M., Paulus, M., Richte, J., Trüby, J., & Lindenberger, D., 2011, 'Energy Policy Scenarios to Reach Challenging Climate Protection Targets in the German Electricity Sector Until 2050', *Utilities Policy* 19, 185-192.
- NDRC, 2007, *Medium and long-term development plan for renewable energy in China*, National Development and Reform Commission of the People's Republic of China, Beijing.
- Oxford Dictionary, n.d., *Climate Emergency*, viewed 30 May 2020, from <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/climate-emergency>.
- Peters, G., Andrew, R., & Korsbakken, J.J., 2019, 'China's CO2 emissions grew slower than expected in 2018', Carbonbrief.org, viewed 17 May 2020, from <https://www.carbonbrief.org/guest-post-chinas-co2-emissions-grew-slower-than-expected-in-2018>.
- Pettigrew, A., 1990, 'Longitudinal field research on change: Theory and practice', *Organization Science* 1 (3), 267-292.
- Population city, 2020, *Freiburg population*, viewed 18 April 2020, from <http://population.city/germany/freiburg/>.
- Porter, M.E., 1990, 'The Competitive Advantage of Nation', *Harvard Business Review*, March-April, 73-91.
- Porter, M.E., 1995, 'The Competitive Advantage of the Inner City', *Harvard Business Review*, May-June, 53-72.
- Quitow, L., Canzler, W., Grundmann, P., Leibenath, M., Moss, T., & Tilmann, R., 2016, 'The German Energiewende – What's Happening? Introducing the Special Issue', *Utilities Policy* 41, 163-171.
- Rave, T., & Albrecht-Saavedra, J., 2015, 'Die Diffusion von Politikinnovationen: Fallstudie zum „Schönauer Modell“ [The diffusion of policy innovations: Case study on the "Schönau Model"]', Ifo.de, viewed 7 April 2020, from

- <https://www.ifo.de/publikationen/2015/working-paper/die-diffusion-von-politikinnovationen-fallstudie-zum-schoenauer>.
- REN21-REC, 2019, *Renewables in Cities 2019 global status report*, viewed 10 February 2020, from https://www.ren21.net/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/REC-2019-GSR_Full_Report_web.pdf.
- REN21, 2019, *Renewables 2019 global status report*, viewed 10 February 2020, from <https://www.ren21.net/gsr-2019/>.
- Renewable Energies Agency, 2019, *Key facts about the energy transition in Germany*, viewed 3 April 2020, from https://2019.energydialogue.berlin/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/betd_press_factsheet.pdf.
- Ritchie, H., & Roser, M., 2020, 'CO₂ and greenhouse gas emissions', Ourworldindata.org, viewed 10 February 2020, from <https://ourworldindata.org/co2-and-other-greenhouse-gas-emissions>.
- Roseland, M., 1997, 'Dimensions of the Eco-City', *Cities*, 14 (4), 197-202.
- Thomas, A., 2012, 'Freiburg green city. Integrated leadership = sustainability leader', Wwf.panda.org, viewed 17 April 2020, from <https://wwf.panda.org/?204419/Freiburg-green-city>.
- UBA, 2019, *Indicator greenhouse gas emissions at a glance*, viewed 14 April 2020, from <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/en/indicator-greenhouse-gas-emissions#at-a-glance>.
- UN, 2019, *Renewable energy investment in 2018 hit USD 288.9 billion, far exceeding fossil fuel investment*, viewed 26 March 2020, from <https://www.unenvironment.org/news-and-stories/press-release/renewable-energy-investment-2018-hit-usd-2889-billion-far-exceeding>.
- UN, 2020, *Flagship UN study shows accelerating climate change on land, sea and in the atmosphere*, viewed 26 April 2020, from <https://news.un.org/en/story/2020/03/1059061>.
- UNEP, 2019, *Chinese initiative Ant Forest wins UN Champions of the Earth award*, viewed 19 May 2020, from <https://www.unenvironment.org/news-and-stories/press-release/chinese-initiative-ant-forest-wins-un-champions-earth-award>.
- UNFCCC, 2018, *What is the Paris Agreement?*, viewed 22 April 2020, from <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/what-is-the-paris-agreement>.
- Uni-Freiburg, 2018, *Sustainable use of resources requires the University library to close at night*, viewed 15 May 2020, from <http://www.pr.uni-freiburg.de/pm-en/press-releases-2018/sustainable-use-of-resources-requires-the-university-library-to-close-at-night>.
- Ydersbond, I.M., & Korsnes, M.S., 2016, 'What Drives Investment in Wind Energy? A Comparative Study of China and the European Union', *Energy Research & Social Science* 12, 50–61.
- Young, O., 1991, 'Political Leadership and Regime Formation: On the Development of Institutions in International Society', *International Organization* 45 (3), 2-85.
- 中华人民共和国住房和城乡建设部 [MOHURD], 2009, *谱写绿色遂宁活力遂宁和谐遂宁新篇章——四川省遂宁市创建国家园林城市侧记 [Write a new chapter in green Suining, vitality in Suining, harmony in Suining—A national garden city record of Suining city, Sichuan Province]*, viewed 31 May 2020, from http://www.mohurd.gov.cn/dfxx/200910/t20091021_196064.html.

- 中国天气网 [China Economic Net], 2010, 富煤少气”的中国如何成功实现能源结构转型 [*How China with "rich coal and less gas" successfully achieves energy structure transformation*], viewed 15 May 2020, from <http://www.weather.com.cn/climate/qhbhyw/08/833716.shtml>.
- 中国报告网 [China Report Net], 2018, 我国大力发展清洁能源, 成为全球清洁能源投资第一大国 [*China vigorously develops clean energy and becomes the largest country in global clean energy investment*], viewed 18 May 2020, from <http://news.chinabaogao.com/nengyuan/201802/02131Q432018.html>.
- 中国石油新闻中心 [CNPC], 2019, 中国原油进口量位居世界首位 [*China's crude oil imports rank first in the world*], viewed 18 May 2020, from <http://news.cnpc.com.cn/system/2019/12/18/001756105.shtml>.
- 中国经济网, [China Economic Net], 2016, 2030年我国非化石能源占比将达到两成 [*The proportion of non-fossil energy in my country will reach 20% by 2030*], viewed 14 June 2020, from <http://www.china-nengyuan.com/news/101034.html>.
- 光明日报 [Guangming Daily], 2019, 奋进, 决胜全面建成小康社会 [*Forge ahead, determine victory and build a well-off society in an all-round way*], viewed 20 May 2020, from <http://cpc.people.com.cn/n1/2019/0228/c415067-30907236.html>.
- 刘东国 [Liu, D.], 2008, ‘中国作为负责任大国如何承担环境责任’ [How China, as a Responsible big Country, Assumes Environmental Responsibility], Journal of School of International Relations, viewed 31 May 2020, from <http://www.cnki.com.cn/Article/CJFDTotat-LUYE200804008.htm>.
- 四川在线 [Sichuan Online], 2018, 《四川省人民政府办公厅关于优化区域产业布局的指导意见》解读一 [*Interpretation I of the Guiding Opinions of the General Office of the Sichuan Provincial Government on Optimizing the Distribution of Regional Industries*], viewed 14 June 2020, from <http://www.sc.gov.cn/10462/10464/13298/13301/2018/12/15/10464905.shtml>.
- 国务院 [State Council], 2013, 国务院关于印发能源发展“十二五”规划的通知 [*Notice of the State Council on Printing and Distributing the "Twelfth Five-Year Plan" for Energy Development*], viewed 15 May 2020, from http://www.gov.cn/zwggk/2013-01/23/content_2318554.htm.
- 国务院 [State Council], 2014, 国务院办公厅关于印发能源发展战略行动计划（2014-2020年）的通知 [*Notice of the General Office of the State Council on Printing and Distributing the Energy Development Strategic Action Plan (2014-2020)*], viewed 16 May 2020, http://www.gov.cn/zhengce/content/2014-11/19/content_9222.htm.
- 国务院办公厅 [General Office of the State], 2006, ‘十一五’环境保护的具体措施 [*Specific Measures for Environmental Protection in the "Eleventh Five-Year Plan"*], viewed 18 May 2020, http://www.gov.cn/node_11140/2006-03/18/content_230163.htm.
- 国务院新闻办公室网站 [SCIO], 2015, 2030年左右二氧化碳排放达到峰值 [*China ensures that carbon dioxide emissions will peak around 2030*], viewed 15 May 2020, from <http://www.scio.gov.cn/video/gxbb/34056/Document/1462082/1462082.htm>.

国家发展改革委 [NDRC], 2016, 国家发展改革委 国家能源局关于印发《能源生产和消费革命战略（2016-2030）》的通知 [*Notice of the National Energy Administration of the National Development and Reform Commission on printing and distributing the "Energy Production and Consumption Revolution Strategy (2016-2030)"*], viewed 15 May 2020, from https://www.ndrc.gov.cn/xxgk/zcfb/tz/201704/t20170425_962953.html.

新华社 [Xinhua News], 2014, 国务院办公厅印发《能源发展战略行动计划（2014-2020年）》 [*General Office of the State Council on Printing and Distributing the Energy Development Strategic Action Plan (2014-2020)*], viewed 18 May 2020, from https://baike.baidu.com/reference/16173989/daa1LtCQU9tVHxxO7KwB1dR-6X1ioVPe6p81z5poYsefs1QbHMqcHjq8S6iU3mrNp7d7VV7_fJNc3eOsqgtms_qvrIwiVe8c5-1ZZ2N--VYO4ZTq.

科技日报 [Technology Daily], 2019, 中国加大可再生能源与新能源国际合作 [*China increases international cooperation in renewable and new energy*], viewed 14 June 2020, from <http://m.people.cn/n4/2019/0822/c4051-13104644.html>.

能源局网站 [Energy Bureau], 2017, ‘能源局发布《能源发展“十三五”规划》等’ [*The Energy Bureau released the "13th Five-Year Plan for Energy Development", etc.*], viewed 31 May 2020, from http://www.gov.cn/xinwen/2017-01/05/content_5156795.htm#1.

董小迪, [Dong, X.], 2019, ‘中国发布 | 国家能源局：2020年我国非化石能源占一次能源消费总量比重将达15%’ [China released | National Energy Administration: my country's non-fossil energy will account for 15% of total primary energy consumption in 2020], News.china.com, viewed 14 June 2020, from http://news.china.com.cn/txt/2019-09/20/content_75228079.htm.

遂宁传媒网 [SCSNTV], 2019, 我是遂宁 | 千年文化浸润心灵 [*I am Suining | Millennium culture infiltrates the soul*], viewed 14 June 2020, from <http://www.scsntv.com/bencandy.php?aid=39177&fid=158>.

遂宁新闻网 [Suining News Network], 2018, 从“居中不通”到成渝重要交通枢纽 [*From "nowhere to connect in the middle" to an important transportation hub in Chengdu and Chongqing*], viewed 31 May 2020, from <http://www.suining.gov.cn/web/sn/snzx/-/articles/4604264.shtml>.

遂宁集约化网站群 [Suining Intensive Website Group], 2019, 主站--绿色遂宁--全球绿色城市 [*Main Station--Green Suining--Global Green City*], viewed 20 May 2020, from <http://www.suining.gov.cn/web/sn/-9/-/articles/3677006.shtml>.